

A Framework for Women's Health Engineering Education: Pedagogical Foundations and Practical Implementation

Brianne K. Connizzo^{1,2*}, Shannon D. Barker³, Juan Gnecco^{4,5},
Carolyn L. Bayer⁶, Christine M. O'Brien⁷, Michelle L. Oyen⁸

¹Department of Biomedical Engineering, Boston University, Boston, MA, USA

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Boston University, Boston, MA, USA

³Department of Biomedical Engineering, University of Virginia, Charlottesville, VA, USA

⁴Department of Biomedical Engineering, Tufts University, Medford, MA, USA

⁵Woman, Mother & Baby (WoMB) Research Institute, Tufts Medical Center, Boston, MA, USA

⁶Department of Biomedical Engineering, Tulane University, New Orleans, LA, USA

⁷Department of Biomedical Engineering, Washington University in St. Louis, St. Louis, MO, USA

⁸Department of Biomedical Engineering, Wayne State University, Detroit, MI, USA

*Corresponding Author:

Brianne K. Connizzo

Boston University

44 Cummington Mall, ERB 403

Boston, MA 02215

connizzo@bu.edu

ORCID: 0000-0002-7818-0537

Abstract

Women represent more than half the U.S. workforce, yet women's health research and education remain systematically underprioritized, hindering technological innovation in this domain. Recent policy initiatives have elevated the profile of women's health and created urgency for engineering education to align with this shift. Despite growing recognition that advanced engineering approaches are essential to address sex-specific diseases and physiological differences, most biomedical engineering students graduate without exposure to women's health as a thematic focus or to the clinical problems and existing solutions in this space. To address this gap, we present a systematic review and best practices guide based on six independently designed women's health engineering courses. Drawing on pedagogical literature and collective teaching experience, we document core elements and provide practical frameworks for both standalone women's health courses and integration into existing biomedical engineering curricula. This work is designed to lower the barrier for action, such that institutions can implement women's health engineering education scaled to their capacity and constraints. By training engineers to recognize and address systematic gaps in women's health engineering, we prepare them to build the life-changing technologies that women have long been waiting for.

Key Terms: women's health engineering, biomedical engineering education, reproductive health, sex differences, inclusive design, human-centered design, active learning

I. Introduction

Women represent approximately 50 percent of the U.S. population and 56.8 percent of the workforce,¹ yet women's health research and workforce education remains a taboo and unprioritized topic that has hindered advances in women's health. In this review, we use "women's health" here to refer to the health of individuals with female reproductive anatomy, regardless of gender identity, as it remains the dominant terminology in clinical research, funding structures, and educational frameworks. However, we acknowledge that this term is imperfect and may inadvertently exclude the experiences of transgender and non-binary individuals. Women's health - defined as diseases and conditions that affect women only, affect women differently, or affect women disproportionately - has been hindered by the lack of educational integration into interdisciplinary disciplines in STEM education which have limited advances in biomedical sciences and medicine (Fig. 1).[1] Fortunately, interest in women's health as a specific thematic topic in biomedical research has been growing rapidly over the last decade. Notably, within this whole-body framework, reproductive health is not the sole focus of women's health but one of many important systemic topics[2] including, but not limited to, different presentation of cardiovascular disease, greater occurrence of osteoporosis, the need for sex-based drug dosing, differences in immune system responses and autoimmune disease, disproportionate rates of mental health afflictions, and many more.

Historically, the focus of women's health training has largely centered on reproductive health in the form of midwives, and the history of training in midwifery goes back millennia to Egypt and Rome.[3, 4] The more modern interest in women's health coincided with the emergence of second wave feminism.[5] It accelerated in the US in the 1990s with the first female director of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) and the establishment of the NIH Office of Research in Women's Health in 1993. Around this time, female representation in Congress was also increasing, and bipartisan efforts to address breast cancer were established.[6] The topic of women's health started to accelerate in growth again in the late 2010s, as several key thought-leaders recognized discrepancies in research and funding between diseases and conditions that affect men and those that affect women.[7, 8] This was fostered by the 2016 NIH policy on Sex as a Biologic Variable (SABV), which required researchers to include both female and male animals, cells, and human subjects in NIH-funded preclinical

Figure 1. Definition of disorders that fall under the classification of 'women's health' research

and clinical research. This burst was further propagated by significant support from Presidential efforts in 2023-2024 to advance this space.[9] A comprehensive National Academies of Engineering, Science, and Medicine (NASEM) report in early 2025 recommended significant Congressional budgetary investment in women's health research and development.[10] The NASEM report contained extensive quantitative evaluation of funding trends, showing that less than 10% of research funding addresses women's health and that this proportion was going down even as the overall NIH budget was increasing.

Within this alignment and prioritization of women's health it became evident that advanced engineering approaches including tools and frameworks were useful and, in many cases, necessary to address the systemic, dynamic and complex biology of females and these tools would be particularly well-suited for women's health research. Unfortunately, due to constraints, including funding, women's health research and engineering have been historically siloed with limited overlap between the clinical and biological problems and potential tools, methods and technologies that can help solve these problems. A clear example of this is the reliance on the use of animals that generally do not menstruate or undergo menopause, and have estrous hormone cycles rather than the menstrual cycles experienced by humans. The push for opportunities in generating humanized model systems - the so-called NAMs, "New Approach Methodologies," – aims to reduce the use of animal models and create more human-relevant results.[11] The broad category of NAMs includes hot topics such as AI/ML, big data, digital twins and other physics-based computational models, 'omics measurements and models, and in vitro techniques using human cells. This is just one example of an opportunity wherein engineering is poised to take a leading role in advancing women's health research, however many other opportunities remain unmet.

A recent report from McKinsey estimated that the scale of potential boost to the US economy from investing in women's health is one trillion dollars[2] and this is framed against a documented long history of poor investment in women's health. An active "FemTech" Industry has been emerging in the last decade,[12] providing potential job opportunities for college graduates. Engineers, mathematicians, and computer scientists have been working in women's health fields for many years without the existence of a formal sub-field within biomedical engineering.[13] However, with the recent emphasis on women's health, there have been increasing efforts to organize within the biomedical engineering community to centralize and culture the exchange of information and foster collaboration across disciplines and in new fields. As women's health continues to grow within the biomedical engineering research community, it is critical to integrate these topics within engineering education and workforce development. This manuscript is written by six professors of biomedical engineering who have designed and led their own courses focused on women's health engineering. In this manuscript, we present

established pedagogical approaches and practical considerations to help other educators initiate their own independent courses and/or to incorporate women's health content into an existing biomedical engineering curriculum.

II. Current Landscape of Women's Health Education

A. Pedagogical Principles for Women's Health Education

A foundational guidance document from the U.S. Department of Health & Human Services (HSS)' Office of Women's Health and the Health Resources & Services Administration (HRSA),[14] released in 2013, recommended that women's health curricula incorporate three key principles (1) lifespan approach—recognizing that women's health changes dramatically across development, puberty, reproduction, menopause, and aging; (2) social determinants of health (SDH)—addressing how social, economic, and environmental factors shape health inequities and access to care; and (3) cultural considerations—recognizing how health outcomes vary with demographic characteristics, identity, and lived experience. These principles, originally developed for medical education, apply equally to engineering education. Beyond these foundational principles, pedagogical research supports the effectiveness of approaches specifically suited to complex, multidisciplinary topics like women's health: feminist and gender-responsive pedagogy,[15–18] which makes gender visible as a technical variable and challenges male-normed assumptions embedded in research data, design standards, and engineering curricula; health equity frameworks,[19, 20] which situate engineering problem definitions within the social, economic, and political forces that shape women's health outcomes; and active learning approaches,[21, 22] which deepen conceptual understanding and make abstract concepts tangible and socially relevant.

B. Current State of Women's Health Education Across Disciplines

Women's health education exists across higher education, though its integration into engineering remains quite limited. Medical schools offer dedicated women's health courses, with Yale University's foundational course offered first in 1994 serving as an influential model for interdisciplinary approaches.[23] The course's stated goals evolved from inspiring students to pursue careers in women's health to providing a critically framed public education in women's health issues, and it remains a useful model for how lecture-based courses can engage students across technical and non-technical backgrounds on the full spectrum of women's health topics. Programs at the Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health and Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health offer standalone courses in women's health alongside integrated modules in pathophysiology and epidemiology courses. Additionally, several medical schools across the nation have begun to offer a Women's Health Scholarly Concentration, which fosters self-directed learning parallel to the core curriculum.

In engineering, women’s health education is only just emerging. Physiology courses at the University of Virginia[24] and University of California San Diego (UCSD) have integrated women’s health examples into core technical content, while design courses at UCSD and University of Michigan have incorporated projects focusing on women’s health. However, these remain scattered and difficult to identify in course catalogs, reflecting a lack of systematic framework for integrating women’s health into the traditional biomedical engineering curriculum. This review documents eight independently-designed women's health engineering courses across research universities (Table 1), systematizes the pedagogical approaches that emerged, and provides actionable frameworks for other BME educators. We identify two complementary pathways: (1) developing a dedicated standalone women's health engineering course, and (2) integrating women's health content into existing technical curricula.

III. Running an Independent Course

To our knowledge, there have been eight independently-designed and directed standalone women’s health engineering courses offered (Table 1), six of which were offered by the authors of this paper and seven of which were offered for the first time in the last 5 years. These have been varied in terms of level of instruction (from first year undergraduates to second year doctoral students), content, and format. It’s also important to note that these courses were all offered at R1 institutions with high research effort. However, several strong themes have emerged from these courses. Therefore, the content in this section reflects strategies the authors have found successful in establishing an independent women’s health engineering course, and could serve as a reference for future course development.

Table 1. Independent course offerings on women’s health engineering (shaded boxes represent the courses offered by this manuscript’s authors)

Course Title	University/College	Offered	Students
BME 5060: Engineering for Women's Health	Wayne State University	2025-present	Upper Level Undergraduates, Masters, Doctoral
BME 4550: Engineering Women’s Health	University of Virginia	2025-present	Upper Level Undergraduates
BE500-A3: Women’s Health in Biomedical Engineering	Boston University	2025-present	Upper Level Undergraduates, Masters, Doctoral
ENGR 307: Engineering for Women's Health	Stanford University	2025-present	Masters, Doctoral

BME 5780: Engineering for Women's Health	Washington University in St Louis	2024-present	Upper Level Undergraduates, Masters, Doctoral
BMEN 6660: Bioengineering of Women's Reproductive Health	Tulane University	2024-present	Masters, Doctoral
EN1-0017: Frontiers In Reproductive Engineering (FIRE)	Tufts University	2022-present	First Year Undergraduates
Engineering 39D: Designing Technology for Girls and Women	University of California, Berkeley	2003	First & Second Year Undergraduates

A. Recruitment and Retention of Students

It's well known that recruiting a diverse body of students is critical for fostering an inclusive learning environment, and women's health engineering is no exception. A successful independent course should prioritize attracting not only students interested in women's health but also a diverse and wide range of student populations, including balanced female/male student ratios, international students, and first-generation college attendees. It is important to recognize that while male students are often less represented in discussions on women's health, they play a vital role in addressing engineering challenges in this area as topics discussed are often systemic, translate across diseases/conditions, and generally impact the advancement of human health. Rough enrollment estimates in our courses reported that nearly three quarters of our students were female (Fig. 2). This is in contrast to enrollment numbers and undergraduate degrees awarded in many engineering disciplines, which skew heavily towards male students.[25] Likewise, international students bring unique perspectives on global health issues that translate across cultural divides, which enrich discussions and reflection points particularly relating to women's healthcare. Finally, first-generation students often contribute valuable viewpoints rooted in diverse life experiences, and for some it may be the first time encountering these topics, including sexual health. Strategies that have been used by the authors include a clear and defined syllabus and course summary to explicitly define the topics to be discussed. For example, particular emphasis can be made on the role of sex hormones on non-reproductive organ systems, such as the cardiovascular, musculoskeletal, and neurological tissues. In addition, targeted advertisement in required courses to increase reach as well as marketing materials that can help emphasize the importance of inclusivity in women's health engineering and its impact on engineering design principles.

The courses that have been offered independently covering women’s health topics report high enrollment numbers due to the significant interest surrounding the field (Fig. 2). In fact, several of the courses were oversubscribed with waitlists well into the semester. Students recognize the pressing biomedical and engineering challenges in this area and the vast potential for innovation and impact. The enthusiasm of the students is evident not only in the course attendance (Fig. 2) but also in their active engagement during lectures, discussions, and projects. Course evaluations show that many students believe the course content aligns with their desire to make meaningful contributions to underserved areas of healthcare (Fig. 2). The intersection of technical engineering principles and the opportunity to address real-world health disparities resonates strongly. However, it’s important to note that longitudinal assessment of learning outcomes and career trajectory requires longer follow-up since many of these courses have only run for 1-2 years.

B. Critical Topic Areas

A comprehensive curriculum in women’s health engineering must incorporate key scientific topics that address female-specific health issues and sex-based differences in health and disease (Fig. 2). Core content should include discussion of basic biology not covered in other courses, including sexual differentiation, reproduction, and endocrinology, while specially highlighting areas that 1) remain poorly understood, and why, and 2) epitomize an engineering problem design parameter. Discussion of specific disease areas should include, but is not limited to, reproductive cancers, breast cancer, gynecologic disorders, urogynecologic disorders, infertility, pregnancy & postpartum,

Figure 2. (left) Statistics on enrollment numbers and demographics, course evaluations and attendance for the authors’ courses over the past four years. (right) Suggested topics for inclusion in a standalone engineering women’s health class.

hormonal transitions (e.g. puberty, menopause), cardiovascular disease, immune function, musculoskeletal disease, and sexual dysfunction. Understanding the underlying physiology and mechanisms of these conditions enables students to develop engineering approaches that specifically address these challenges. It's important to note that this list is by no means exhaustive, and should be updated often with current literature.

Most of the courses designed incorporated ethics discussions in the courses described. Ethical considerations are a cornerstone of any engineering curriculum, but particularly so for women's health content due to its sensitive nature and historical barriers that have hindered advances in this space including fertility, reproduction, and access to healthcare technologies. Students should be encouraged to evaluate how engineered products are designed, marketed, and potentially weaponized in harmful ways. For example, discussions should include the ethical implications surrounding fertility treatments, genetic testing, and wearable reproductive health technologies with specific references to historical cases and discussions of context and ethics of figures such as Dr. J Marion Sims, Henrietta Lacks, and Margaret Sanger.[26–28]

In addition, women's health outcomes are shaped by many intersecting identities and structural inequities and exist globally, driven by factors such as race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, geographic location, disability status, gender identity, and immigration status. For example, low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) often face disparities in healthcare, with delayed diagnoses, insufficient resources, and poor access contributing to worse outcomes.[29–31] . Emphasizing the design of accessible and affordable technologies for low-resource settings ensures that students consider the global applicability and equity of their solutions.[32, 33] Further, statistics on conditions such as cervical cancer, maternal mortality, and osteoporosis, which have significant racial and socioeconomic disparities, should be incorporated into the curriculum. Students should analyze how engineering solutions may inadvertently perpetuate or amplify existing inequities if they do not account for diverse user needs and social contexts.

Finally, it is important to consider that the process of *engineering* devices or technologies for these disorders will inherently include designing for a unique population of users, particularly for addressing female-specific concerns. Using case studies as an active learning approach,[34] students can analyze technical design flaws that arise from excluding diverse perspectives and find opportunities for much needed innovation. One such example is the development of the speculum, a product originally engineered through unethical means and without adequate input from female users. These discussions are valuable for identifying ways to mitigate challenges and better align product development with user needs. This could also include discussion of products that are not historically designed to be sex-specific, such as seat belts,[35–37] sports equipment,[38–40] and even implantable devices[41, 42] that have been determined to be inappropriate for female anatomy and physiology. Further, this should also include

discussion of user error, compliance, and social and cultural preferences; this might be particularly relevant for a new contraceptive device or a vaginal drug delivery systems.[43–45] These considerations are often overlooked in women’s health, but should be a critical part of an independent course on the subject.

C. Learning Objectives

Before establishing a framework for the course, it is essential to establish clear, measurable learning outcomes that align with course goals. Here are some example goals for the classes that have been organized by the authors herein:

- Students should be able to describe the current understanding of biological mechanisms, disease pathophysiology, and engineering principles relevant to women's health
- Students should demonstrate the ability to define engineering principles and apply them to address women's health challenges
- Students should be able to critically analyze women’s health engineering technologies to assess their potential and limitations to demonstrate their problem solving capacity within a specific need area
- Students should be able to evaluate existing technologies, research, and policies through a lens of equity and inclusion
- Students should effectively communicate technical concepts to diverse audiences and work collaboratively on complex problems

D. Key Course Elements (Fig. 3)

Evidence-Based Learning: Given the limited research in the field of women’s health engineering, it is imperative that the course introduces students to primary literature, emphasizing recent advancements and current research gaps. Encouraging students to critically engage with these studies not only enhances their understanding but also inspires innovation.[21, 46, 47] Practical examples of ways to incorporate primary literature into a standalone course include written critiques (addressing study design, limitations, and engineering implications), journal club presentations where groups lead class discussion, and synthesis assignments comparing 3-5 papers to identify consensus, contradictions, and engineering opportunities. Similarly, students can present clinical or engineering case study analyses, requiring students to identify problems, analyze contributing factors including sex bias, and propose interventions. Cases that evolve throughout the semester may enable the students to demonstrate deepening understanding and adaptive problem-solving.

Women’s health issues are by the very nature multifaceted, systemic, socio-technical problems; and case-based and problem-based learning require students to interpret complex health contexts involving societal, ethical, cultural, and technical factors. Case

studies are essential for illustrating the diversity and complexity of women’s health challenges, from variability in patient experiences to the real-world difficulties in diagnosis and treatment.[48, 49] Case-based learning also uses specific contextualized cases that reflect real situations to anchor discussions and learning.[50] These cases foster discussion on the multifactorial nature of women’s health disorders and highlight the importance of considering sex-specific factors in biomedical engineering.[51] They also help students apply theoretical knowledge to a specific problem and to build self-directed learning, collaboration, and problem-solving skills.[49, 52–54] They also teach students to contextualize engineering concepts within real clinical challenges or device failures, enabling them to bridge the gap between scientific and engineering principles in authentic scenarios.[34, 55] Such methods encourage critical thinking, deepen conceptual understanding, and make abstract engineering concepts tangible and socially relevant.[56, 57]

Design-Based Learning: Project-based and design-centered active learning strategies[58–60] engages students in extended investigations of complex, real-world problems, often culminating in student-developed designs and solutions.[59, 61, 62] In engineering education, these approaches mirror the professional practice of engineers solving real societal challenges and supports deeper cognitive engagement and critical thinking.[63–66] Examples of this kind of learning in engineering often involve needs-finding, ideation, prototyping and iteration, and presenting outcomes through design proposals or pitches.[58, 67–70] Women’s health, whether focused on biomedical devices, community health systems, health informatics, or policy implications, can be framed as authentic engineering design challenges, which align well with these design steps, continuing to help students move content from purely theoretical knowledge to applied problem-solving.[71] Human-centered design is essential for women’s health projects as they involves students

	Independent EWH Course	Existing Course
Evidence-Based Learning	Include Recent News and Literature	
		Incorporate WH Papers in Class Readings
Project-Based Learning	Incorporate Design or Lab-Based Projects	
		Include and Encourage WH Design Ideas
Ethics & Empathic Design	Include Case Studies in WH Failures	
		Discuss Sex-Specific Use or Design
Expert & Industry Opinion	Incorporate Frequent Guest Lectures	
		Consider WH + FemTech Guest Lectures

Figure 3. Recommendations on how to incorporate women’s health content into a standalone or an existing engineering course.

designing solutions around the needs, experiences, and challenges of real people rather than assuming what is needed.[72] This type of design is what's largely been missing in women's health for some time.

Course projects can address vast topics such as developing better diagnostic tools for menopause, developing better approaches for model systems, or improving drug delivery mechanisms for reproductive health disorders. Several of the courses offered by authors included a semester-long design project centered around women's health needs. These projects were often mentioned in course evaluations to be the most rewarding of the assignments as the open-ended nature of the project allowed students to explore areas outside of lecture.[69] Use phased deliverables (needs assessment, literature review, preliminary designs, final design) for formative feedback rather than single final submissions. Design notebooks document iterative thinking, sketches, and reflections. Prototype demonstrations assess technical execution and user-centered features. Technical reports should evaluate design specifications, integration of women's health considerations, and communication quality. Importantly, students should be given feedback on product designs (and research strategies) early and often given the highly dynamic nature of the field as well as the lack of basic literature on some disorders and diseases.

Laboratory Research Modules: The application of engineering principles may be best achieved through hands-on research-like experiences, such as one of the author's courses that incorporated laboratory modules centered in women's health research. To increase engagement and translation from theory to practice physical demonstrations, whether in the lab, or instruments, should be provided. For example, lab tours have provided an excellent way to introduce students to concepts in microfluidics, organs-on-chips (OoCs) and tissue engineering by providing them with physical chips or biomaterials to better understand the material and fabrication processes used in microengineered devices. This gives them a scale reference and a practical introduction to the potential and limitations for these model systems. In another example, exposure to topics in biophonics and 3D imaging was performed by providing the student with sample imaging datasets (publicly available or in house generated) of tissues relating to the female reproductive tract including microCT, fMRIs, light imaging datasets. Exposure to these datasets give students access to 3D imaging analysis pipelines with free software (e.g., FIJI, IMARIS viewer) to better understand the anatomy, imaging modalities, 3D data handling and analytical pipelines. Altogether, these strategies provide accessible and low-cost educational experiences that enable students to be exposed to or work directly with technologies and methodologies used in both academia and industry, and hands-on experiences allow learners to connect theory to practice.

Expert Guest Lectures: The offered courses also found that expert guest lectures were both well-received by students and critical to engagement in the course. In engineering

education, students are encouraged to incorporate stakeholder perspectives through ethnographic observation, interviews, personas, and case studies, fostering ethical and socially responsive engineering practices.[73–75] This is particularly important for women’s health, an area where historical biases in research and technology have led to inequitable outcomes. Engineering programs can bridge this gap by challenging students to recognize gendered aspects of health experiences (through gender-responsive pedagogy[15, 19]), appreciate intersectional health needs linked to age, race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, etc., and to move beyond assumptions to design solutions that align with user needs and values. Interdisciplinary teaching also encourages students to integrate knowledge across disciplines rather than learning in silos, which supports critical thinking, reflective judgement, and complex problem-solving.[76–78] In engineering education, these approaches integrate engineering with biology, clinical sciences, public health, and entrepreneurship.[60, 79–81] A major factor hindering interdisciplinary efforts in education and research is the poor translational communication between engineers, basic scientists, and clinicians. These guest lecture opportunities serve to appreciate the language used by external researchers and find common ground on specific topics.

To best prepare students to lead an impactful and collaborative workforce, we propose that efforts must be made to bridge the gap in dialogue between science and engineering disciplines. Guest lectures provide students with specialized insights into topics that a large majority of biomedical engineering faculty may not have experience with, such as gynecology, reproduction, and endocrinology. This also helps students and faculty to identify more connections between traditional engineering disciplines and women’s health engineering. Instructors and guest lecturers can highlight the most recent advancements, gaps in the field, and emerging opportunities for students to contribute. Further, guest lectures also provide an opportunity to integrate students with clinical and industrial sectors to demonstrate the practical application of their education.[82, 83] Connections to the FemTech industry illustrate the career landscape and potential for innovation, while clinical partnerships give students invaluable insight into real-world processes like the diagnostic journey and treatment planning for women’s health disorders. Further, networking opportunities with these experts can facilitate future collaborations and open doors to jobs or graduate positions. Complementing this external expertise, reflective writing assignments based on lectures can help students internally process challenging material and examine their own assumptions through structured prompts about ethics, bias, and changed perspectives, or through perspective-taking exercises where they write from stakeholder viewpoints (e.g., a patient letter to a design team). Reflections should be assessed on depth of thinking and genuine engagement rather than "correct" answers, evaluating students' awareness of complexity and articulation of personal growth throughout the course.

Encouraged Student Participation: Active student participation is essential in women's health engineering courses, where discussion-based learning and diverse perspectives enrich the understanding of complex, multifaceted health challenges. However, given the sensitive nature of course content and varying student comfort levels, participation assessment must be structured carefully to promote equity and inclusion. Multiple pathways for participation accommodate different learning styles and ensure that all students can meaningfully engage regardless of their comfort discussing intimate health topics in public settings. This might include assessments on in-person class participation, office visits, discussion board participation, attendance at optional events, and private reflections on guest lectures.

Preparation checks ensure students come to class ready to engage with course material. For example, brief quizzes on assigned literature reviews can verify that students have read and engaged with the content before discussion, as implemented in one course. Discussion board posts before class sessions serve a similar function while allowing students time to formulate thoughtful responses. These low-stakes assessments hold students accountable for preparation without creating excessive pressure. During class discussions, structured approaches can make participation more equitable and productive than subjective participation grades. Assigning discussion roles such as summarizer, questioner, and connector gives students specific responsibilities and ensures diverse types of contributions. This structure particularly benefits students who may be less comfortable with spontaneous participation but excel when given defined tasks. Incorporating peer-to-peer evaluation—such as having students provide constructive feedback on each other's presentations or design proposals using structured rubrics—can help students develop critical evaluation skills they will need as professional engineers.

D. Challenges and Barriers

Developing and teaching a women's health engineering course presents unique challenges that differ from traditional biomedical engineering coursework. Based on collective experiences of the authors and feedback from colleagues implementing similar courses, we identify common challenges and offer practical solutions.

Limited Instructor Expertise in Women's Health Content: Most biomedical engineering faculty have not received formal training in women's health topics, reproductive biology, or gynecologic disorders. This can create anxiety about teaching outside one's expertise and concerns about accuracy when discussing complex biological systems. Some solutions might include systematically reviewing recent consensus papers and textbooks in women's health, partnering with faculty from clinical departments who can provide biological context, and engaging experts outside of the community in the classroom. Reframe the course as a learning opportunity to explore fundamental and systemic

biological emerging topics alongside the student, which can enhance student engagement. To keep course content up to date, you may choose to join emerging special interest groups focused on women's health at national engineering conferences to stay informed, such as the Biomedical Engineering Society (BMES) Special Interest Group (SIG).

Student Discomfort with Sensitive Topics: Women's health involves discussing topics like menstruation, pregnancy, sexual function, and intimate medical procedures that some students find uncomfortable. It's important to note that the authors of this manuscript have not found this to be widely true. Often students are excited to discuss these topics and appreciate the forum to do so. Nevertheless, it's worth discussing practice strategies should this arise. Set expectations early, acknowledging that the course covers sensitive topics and establish guidelines for respectful and professional discussion. Presenting content in clinical, scientific, and professional language can help to reduce stigma surrounding the discussion of these topics. Provide context for why these discussions are important and emphasize how women's health principles apply to engineering more broadly.

Lack of Existing Course Materials and Resources: Unlike established biomedical engineering topics with abundant textbooks, problem sets, and teaching materials, women's health engineering has limited pedagogical resources and therefore faculty must create new material. We have compiled some useful textbooks for the integration of women's health content with engineering ([Supplemental Table 1](#)). In addition, existing primary literature can be leveraged as course materials, which also exposes students to cutting-edge work. As you develop materials, consider sharing them through professional organizations, such as the Biomedical Engineering Society (BMES) or the American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE), or other online repositories. You may also consider resource sharing with other instructors teaching similar courses and even engage the students by having them create case studies or design challenges as projects. Hands-on learning may require specialized equipment or biological samples that are expensive, ethically complex, or difficult to obtain for educational purposes. It may be possible to partner with FemTech companies to donate samples or provide facility tours. If not, you may be able to use proxy experiments, computational alternatives, and virtual labs when physical resources are not available.

Balancing Breadth and Depth: Women's health encompasses an enormous range of topics from basic reproductive biology to complex disease states across multiple organ systems. Deciding what to include in a single-semester course is challenging, and instructors may struggle with covering topics superficially versus selecting fewer topics for deeper exploration. Decide what you want to emphasize in your course by identifying core topics to explore deeply; this may depend on the course level; for example, first year undergraduate classes may emphasize breadth while graduate courses emphasize more

depth and critical analysis. You may choose to use this opportunity to encourage self-directed learning, by assigning outside readings that cannot be covered in class.

Institutional Support and Recognition: New courses in women's health engineering may face institutional hurdles including skepticism about academic rigor or difficulty fitting into existing curricula. However, the courses described in this work have been successfully established at institutions that vary significantly in geography (Northeast, Southeast, West Coast, Midwest), funding status (public and private), and student demographics, demonstrating broad applicability and demand across diverse educational contexts. When seeking institutional support, emphasize that women's health is not a niche topic—it encompasses the health of all people, as sex differences research reveals fundamental biological mechanisms (e.g., endocrinology, tissue physiology, mechanics and immunology) that can affect diagnosis, treatment, and outcomes across populations.

To build institutional support, articulate the engineering principles, design skills, and technical competencies developed in the course, as well as how the course addresses ABET outcomes. It may be possible to offer the course initially as a special topic or independent study to demonstrate success before seeking permanent status. Document enrollment numbers, waitlist data, and student outcomes through pre- and post-course surveys. Several instructors found that after one or two successful offerings with strong enrollment and positive evaluations, securing permanent approval became significantly easier. Highlighting student success stories—such as those pursuing women's health research, securing FemTech positions, or developing successful capstone projects—provides concrete evidence of educational impact and career relevance.

IV. Incorporating Women's Health in Current Engineering Courses

Women's health topics can effectively be incorporated into regularly offered courses in the traditional biomedical engineering curriculum. Here we focus on the core classes that might be offered and provide concrete examples and resources for how to incorporate women's health topics into existing activities and develop new ideas within the existing course topics (Table 2).

Table 2. Example topics and suggested reading for incorporation into existing BME courses.

Course	Topic	Related Content
Quantitative Physiology	Endocrine signaling	Reproductive endocrinology & the menstrual cycle
	Immune responses	Sex differences in immunology[84]
	Cardiovascular	Pregnancy-related cardiovascular

	physiology	physiology[85]
	Pain	Sex differences in pain perception[86]
Biomechanics & Mechanobiology	Tissue mechanics	Ligament growth or iris degeneration[87, 88]
	Finite element modeling	Pelvic floor mechanics and prolapse modeling[89, 90]
	Fluid dynamics	Milk flow behavior (lactation)[91]
	Kinematics	Breast biomechanics during exercise[92, 93]
Thermodynamics & Transport	Mass transport	Placental oxygen, nutrient, and drug transport[94, 95]
	Interstitial transport	Lymphedema following breast cancer surgery[96, 97]
	Osmotic transport	Lactation and osmotically driven milk secretion[98, 99]
Biomaterials & Tissue Engineering	Microphysiological systems	In vitro models of the reproductive tract[100]
	Biocompatibility	IUDs and contraceptive device materials[101]
	Tissue engineering	Scaffolds for preterm birth or sex differences in hydrogel adhesion[102–104]
Drug Delivery	Mucosal drug delivery	Intrauterine and vaginal drug delivery[105]
	Multi-compartment	Placental drug transfer and fetal pharmacokinetics[106]
	Controlled release	Hormone delivery or nanoparticle distribution[107, 108]
Signals & Systems	Blind source separation	Fetal ECG extraction[109]
	Signal processing	Preeclampsia, cardiovascular monitoring[110, 111]
	Signal acquisition	Wearable sensors for hormone tracking[112]
Diagnostics & Sensing	Immunoassays	Pregnancy and ovulation tests[113]
	Non-invasive analyses	Menstrual effluent diagnostics[114]

	Electrochemical sensing	Vaginal microbiome and pH sensing[115]
Optics & Imaging	MR imaging	Breast density or autism diagnosis[116, 117]
	X-ray densitometry	Postmenopausal osteoporosis monitoring[118]
	Imaging for LMICs	Pocket colposcope[119]
	Ultrasound physics	Obstetric ultrasound and fetal imaging[120]
Data Science	Dataset bias	Sex-disaggregated clinical datasets[121]
	Time-series analysis	Menstrual cycle wearable data[122]
	Data privacy	Cycle tracking data sharing[123]
Machine Learning & AI	Supervised learning	Sex-specific predictive models for aortic aneurysm[124]
	Deep learning	IVF embryo selection or brain structural imaging[125, 126]
	Digital twins	Pregnancy monitoring[127]
Synthetic Biology & Genetic Engineering	Gene editing	CRISPR for gynecologic cancers[128]
	Microbial engineering	Vaginal microbiome engineering[129]
	Synthetic gene circuits	Cell-based biosensors for pregnancy hormones[130]
Ethics and Regulatory Considerations	Clinical trial design	Change in Ambien dosing[131]
	FDA regulatory pathways	Transvaginal surgical mesh or Dalkon Shield[132, 133]
	Bioethics	Ethics of fertility-based technologies[134]
Design Courses	Human-centered design	Customer interviews (female-focused)[135]
	Industry partnerships	FemTech industry partnerships for authentic design[136]
	Inclusive design	Case studies of male-default design failures[137, 138]

A. Quantitative Physiology

Women's health topics can be seamlessly integrated into quantitative physiology courses by emphasizing sex differences in physiological systems. Recognizing that the endocrine and immune systems are not localized to reproductive organs, it is fundamental to consider these topics in the context of any tissue and disease using systems-based approaches. For example, lectures on cardiovascular physiology can include discussions of sex-based variations in heart disease presentation and prognosis, as well as physiologic response to exercises across the lifespan. Reproductive physiology can be used to represent systemic processes such as hormonal regulation, transport phenomena and pregnancy-related tissue adaptations. Additionally, physiology content typically includes medical pathologies and disorders, which offers opportunities throughout the course to reflect on diagnostic and treatment outcomes and the role engineers have in addressing existing inequities. Disparity-focused assignments can be woven into these topics in a variety of ways: asking students to reflect on a personally meaningful healthcare disparity, to socially contextualize a technical problem statement, or to redesign an existing device to better serve a diverse patient population.[24] Given the fundamental nature of the content, as well as the early position in the core requirements for many programs, quantitative physiology courses are well positioned to be among the first places that students encounter women's health topics. This creates an opportunity to build the mindset that women's health is not a specialty topic but a foundational dimension of engineering practice.

B. Biomechanics and Mechanobiology

Women's health provides compelling applications for biomechanics and mechanobiology and can be incorporated directly into class content by inclusion of real-world examples. For example, in strength of materials, students can analyze structural integrity and load-bearing capacity during pregnancy, including increased joint laxity and altered skeletal loading due to fetal weight gain and body morphometry changes.[139, 140] Fluid mechanics modules might explore how pregnancy-induced blood volume changes affect cardiovascular flow dynamics, the role of uterine blood flow in fetal development, or lactation dynamics.[141] Continuum mechanics could focus on creating growth and remodeling models to predict how soft tissues such as the cervix[142] or pelvic floor[90] adapt under prolonged mechanical stress, such as during labor or high-impact athletic activities.

Lab modules could also be expanded to include biomechanical testing of women's health devices, such as the load-bearing capacity of pelvic floor meshes, rheological properties of vaginal lubricants, or the fatigue life of different sports bra materials. These hands-on activities could also include characterization of reproductive tissues or biofluids. Computational modeling might be more appropriate where limited testing resources are available, and could include finite element and numerical methods. Regardless, integrating these applications into foundational coursework will provide students with a

deeper understanding of how biomechanics intersects with women's health, laying the groundwork for developing targeted, sex-specific solutions.

C. Thermodynamics and Transport

Thermodynamics and transport courses—spanning heat transfer, mass transport, fluid mechanics, and energy balances—offer numerous opportunities to integrate women's health examples that are both clinically meaningful and pedagogically effective. For example, mass transport is central to placental physiology, where oxygen, nutrients, carbon dioxide, and metabolic waste must be continuously exchanged between maternal and fetal circulations across a multilayered barrier.[95] Students can apply Fick's law of diffusion, facilitated and active transport models, and convective-diffusion coupling to analyze how changes in barrier thickness, surface area, or perfusion pressure affect fetal oxygenation—directly relevant to conditions such as intrauterine growth restriction and placental insufficiency. Lactation provides a complementary example, where osmotically and actively driven fluid transport across mammary epithelium—governed by ion gradients and secretory mechanisms—can be used to build quantitative mass balance problems at a physiological interface. Lymphedema—a common complication of axillary lymph node removal following breast cancer surgery—illustrates disrupted interstitial fluid transport and altered Starling forces, extending fluid transport topics beyond the vascular system to the lymphatic and extravascular compartments.

Heat transfer and thermoregulation offer equally compelling applications. Vasomotor symptoms, including hot flashes and night sweats, affect the majority of women during the menopausal transition and result from aberrant hypothalamic thermoregulatory set-point changes, manifesting as abrupt cutaneous vasodilation and sweating. These events map directly onto convective and evaporative heat transfer from the skin surface and can be used to develop quantitative thermal dissipation problems. Thermoregulation is also substantially altered during pregnancy due to increased basal metabolic rate, higher resting core temperature, and altered body composition, providing additional material for energy balance analysis. Finally, cryopreservation of oocytes and embryos in assisted reproductive technology introduces phase transitions, non-isothermal diffusion of cryoprotectants, and optimal cooling rate design as problems in applied thermodynamics, connecting engineering principles to emerging reproductive medicine. Pregnancy and menopause provide some of the richest and most underutilized datasets for teaching transport phenomena.

D. Biomaterials

Biomaterials courses typically cover material classification (metals, ceramics, polymers, and composites), surface chemistry, biocompatibility, host response, degradation behavior, and the regulatory frameworks governing implantable devices. Each of these

topics has direct and well-documented relevance to women's health, where biomaterial design decisions have had consequences ranging from transformative clinical benefit to serious patient harm. Incorporating women's health into biomaterials courses can be achieved by providing real-world examples of types of biomaterials and their challenges. The Dalkon Shield, an intrauterine device designed and distributed in the 1960s-70s,[143, 144] may be the best example of biomaterial design failure. The tail, made of a non-absorbable synthetic surgical suture, enabled accumulation and growth of bacteria, leading to pelvic infections, sepsis, and death. This case is particularly effective because it connects material properties directly to biological failure mechanisms, and challenges students to consider what preclinical testing would have been required to prevent it.

Biomaterial design plays key roles in device fabrication, clinical combability, in vitro modeling, advanced organoid cell culture and drug delivery. Thus, there is a growing body of literature that specifically deploys biomaterials to address unmet medical needs in women's health including top-down and bottom-up approaches. For example, naturally derived and decellularized scaffolds have been explored for uterine and endometrial tissue repair, providing matrix environments that retain native biochemical cues relevant to implantation and hormonal response.[145] Hybrid[146] and fully synthetic biomaterials[147] have also been used to generate three-dimensional endometrial and cervical models that recapitulate tissue mechanics and cellular organization in ways that conventional cell culture cannot. Absorbable polymer systems and lipid-based carriers have also been engineered for localized vaginal and intrauterine drug delivery, where material degradation rate, mucoadhesion, and pH stability under hormonal variation are critical design parameters. Breast implant materials — spanning silicone elastomers to tissue expanders — provide a further case study in long-term biocompatibility and capsular contracture. As biomaterial platforms grow in sophistication, women's health applications will continue to be among the most demanding and consequential test cases for rational biomaterial design.

E. Tissue Engineering

Tissue engineering (TE) aimed at restoring tissue function by integrating engineering principles to biological systems to regenerate and reconstruct faulty tissues,[148] is primarily guided by the paradigm that integrating biomaterials (matrices and scaffolds to mimic tissue extracellular matrix), cells (key biological component of the tissues) and biological signals (biomechanical and molecular cues to activate and guide cell behavior) can lead to building of artificial tissues. While this approach is applicable to any tissue and organ type, the development of engineered models has been particularly impactful in women's health engineering. These TE models overcome the limitation of existing *in vivo* models that generally do not menstruate,[149] do not recapitulate menopausal transition,[150] and do not develop specific diseases like endometriosis. Advances and designs of complex tissue engineered methodologies including hydrogel-based 3D cell

culture, organoids, lab-on-chip, microphysiological systems (MPSs), and other emerging technologies can help address these limitations.

To incorporate women's health in TE courses, we encourage critical reviews of published work depicting engineering design and applications. Specifically, deploying the TE paradigm across biological scales including the cellular level (i.e., the generation of advanced 3D cell culture and organoid systems[151]), multicellular tissue level (multicellular and physiomimetic models[147, 152]), and whole organ level (organ-on-chip and microphysiologic systems[100, 153]) generates a comprehensive understanding of TE. These more complex models have been used to study and recapitulate normal menstrual cycle physiology,[100] as well as to make key discoveries about human conception and fertility.[154, 155] We can also use the TE paradigm to help drive the design criteria for tissue engineering of female reproductive tract disorders in both group design projects and laboratory modules, as discussed earlier. Together this approach helps define the design, scaling, and validation parameters needed to build a tissue and its appropriate microenvironment.

F. Drug Delivery

Biomedical engineers may develop innovative drug delivery carriers and design novel drug delivery methods. However, drug delivery mechanisms and pharmacokinetics differ significantly between women and men, yet many drugs and delivery systems are still primarily tested in male populations or male animal models.[156, 157] Incorporating these biological differences into biomedical engineering curricula can help address this long-standing bias by explicitly exploring sex-specific differences in drug delivery and kinetics, including emerging delivery strategies such as nanocarriers, which show great promise for the treatment of diseases across multiple organ systems.

For example, on average, women have slower gastric emptying and intestinal transit, which may alter drug bioavailability and is an important consideration for oral drug delivery vehicles. Hormonal fluctuations due to menstrual cycles and pregnancy can also affect gastric transport, leading to unanticipated and fluctuating changes in bioavailability.[158, 159] Once transported from the gastrointestinal system to the systemic blood supply, the composition of tissues may affect drug biodistribution and clearance. In addition to reduced size and weight, women typically have a higher percentage of body fat, and a lower total body water content, in comparison to men. This may greatly alter the expected drug pharmacokinetics.[158] These considerations are particularly relevant for nanoparticle-based and sustained-release delivery systems, which rely on predictable tissue partitioning and clearance kinetics. Metabolism of drugs can also be different in men versus women due to changes in enzymatic activity and hormonal modulations. Identifying these changes in drug delivery are an essential first step to designing new drug carriers. Additionally, women often have a lower glomerular filtration rate in

comparison to men, which increases the risk of overdose and adverse drug reactions. An additional and often underemphasized consideration is drug delivery to female-specific anatomical sites, such as vaginal drug delivery, which presents unique challenges and opportunities for localized, targeted therapeutic design.[105] Biomedical engineering can address these challenges through smart drug delivery design, and potentially improve drug safety, efficacy, and equity.

G. Signals, Systems and Bioinstrumentation

The integration of women's health into courses on signals, systems, and bioinstrumentation offers opportunities to examine physiological signals and sensing challenges that differ substantially from traditional biomedical engineering examples. Many signals central to women's health—such as those associated with reproduction, pregnancy, and hormonal cycling—are often weaker, more variable, and more susceptible to noise than standard cardiovascular or neuromuscular signals.[160, 161] These characteristics make women's health applications particularly well-suited for teaching advanced signal processing and system design concepts.

For example, fetal electrocardiography highlights the challenge of extracting a low-amplitude signal embedded within dominant maternal ECG and motion artifacts.[138, 162–164] This application naturally introduces topics such as adaptive filtering, blind source separation, and spectral analysis under low signal-to-noise conditions. Similar challenges arise in uterine electrophysiology, autonomic monitoring during pregnancy, and wearable monitoring of reproductive physiology, where assumptions of stationarity or fixed baselines often do not hold. Physiological norms derived from male populations may not be appropriate for women, reinforcing the importance of population-aware modeling and algorithm development.

Women's health applications also expand the range of sensors and biomarkers considered in bioinstrumentation courses. Hormonal measurements, menstrual-cycle-dependent biomarkers, and reproductive health indicators introduce time-varying baselines that require adaptive calibration and longitudinal analysis. These features provide concrete examples for teaching system identification, drift compensation, and multimodal sensing. In addition, women's health remains an area with significant unmet diagnostic needs. Conditions such as endometriosis, preeclampsia, and gynecologic infections provide case studies where improved sensing and signal interpretation could substantially reduce diagnostic delays or reliance on invasive procedures.[165] Additional examples of novel sensors for women's health technologies are reported in the next section.

Incorporating women's health into signals, systems, and bioinstrumentation courses can be achieved by embedding these applications into core topics rather than adding new

standalone material. In signal-processing modules, students can analyze and filter fetal or uterine electrical signals, compare decomposition methods, or evaluate how noise and motion artifacts affect detection performance. Systems courses can examine wearable monitoring platforms for reproductive health, emphasizing tradeoffs among signal quality, power consumption, cost, and usability. Detection and estimation topics may use hormone tracking or cycle-based biomarkers to illustrate challenges in threshold setting and classification when physiological baselines vary over time. Laboratory modules can also be adapted to include hands-on characterization of women's health sensors and devices, such as evaluating the performance of low-cost electrodes for abdominal recordings, testing disposable point-of-care diagnostics for gynecologic infections, or comparing wearable sensor placement strategies for reproductive health monitoring. These approaches allow students to engage with real-world signal processing and bioinstrumentation challenges while gaining an understanding of how women's health needs can drive innovation in biomedical systems.

H. Diagnostics and Sensing

Women's health diagnostics span multiple sensor modalities (immunosensors, enzyme-based, nucleic acid-based, optical, electrical, thermal) and form factors (lab tests, point-of-care, wearables), providing rich examples for teaching sensor selection and design. Routine point-of-care sensors include the pregnancy test which detects human chorionic gonadotropin and ovulation tests which measure luteinizing hormone for fertility awareness, both of which are immunosensor (antibody-based) lateral flow assays.[166] Modern digitized versions use optical readers to quantify results, which could present a teaching opportunity in optical signal processing. Additional point-of-care tests include proteinuria monitoring via colorimetric dye-binding assays for preeclampsia[167] and culture-based or rapid molecular assays for urinary tract infections.[168] Nucleic acid-based genetic tests of blood or saliva are routinely used for reproductive cancer screening, such as those with a family history of breast or ovarian cancer.[169] Detection of CA-125,[170] a protein elevated in ovarian cancer as well as a variety of other gynecologic conditions,[171] as well as hyperdilution of urine-based tests could be an opportunity to introduce sensor performance metrics, such as sensitivity and specificity. Cervicovaginal fluid-based sensors provide a unique window into the vaginal microbiome,[172–174] but could also be instructive as well given the large dynamic range necessary to distinguish between healthy and infectious samples.

A growing class of women's health monitoring technologies rely on physical sensing modalities, including optical, thermal, mechanical, and electrical sensors, that can be integrated into wearable platforms for continuous or longitudinal use.[165] Optical sensors based on photoplethysmography (PPG) measure volumetric blood flow changes through tissue absorption and scattering of light, forming the basis of wearable heart rate monitors and pulse oximeters widely used during pregnancy and postpartum monitoring. PPG

sensors are also being explored for use in cuffless blood pressure devices.[175] Emerging near infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) sensors are being explored for placental oxygenation monitoring,[176] pelvic floor muscle oxygenation,[177] and breast cancer characterization and detection.[178] Laser speckle contrast imaging wearables measure changes in blood flow and have recently been made wearable to explore detection of postpartum hemorrhage[179] and hypertension.[175] Emerging optical sensors include surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS)-based approaches which are faster and more sensitive than standard-of-care cultures for pathogen identification.[180, 181]

Thermal sensing provides a minimally invasive window into reproductive physiology as basal body temperature rises measurably following ovulation due to the thermogenic effects of progesterone. Continuous wearable temperature sensors such as those integrated into the Oura Ring now enable automated cycle tracking by detecting this shift with greater temporal resolution.[182] Mechanical sensors enable blood pressure monitoring, which is critically important in pregnancy for detecting hypertensive disorders including preeclampsia. The current clinical standard is the pneumatic cuff, however many researchers and startup companies are working towards wearable mechanical cuffless devices with the use of strain gauge and piezoresistive sensors.[183] Mechanical sensors are also used for monitoring abdominal surface pressure changes caused by uterine contractions during labor[184] and clinically in pelvic floor strength assessment and physical therapy.[185]

1. Optics and Imaging

Women's health provides clinically important applications across imaging modalities taught in biomedical optics courses. Reproductive anatomy, breast tissue, and the pregnant body each present unique imaging challenges related to depth, resolution, contrast mechanisms, and anatomical variability, making these applications both technically instructive and directly relevant to large patient populations.

Ultrasound is the most widely used imaging modality in women's health, because of its safety during pregnancy, depth of measurement, portability, and real-time capability. Transvaginal ultrasound provides high-resolution imaging of the uterus, ovaries, and cervix for antral follicle counting in fertility assessment, endometrial thickness measurement, egg retrieval guidance, early gestational monitoring, and cervical length assessment.[186–188] Transabdominal ultrasound tracks fetal growth, placental location and blood flow through doppler ultrasound features, and amniotic fluid volume throughout pregnancy.[189] Breast ultrasound and digital tomosynthesis are increasingly used to support breast cancer evaluation and detection in patients with dense breasts where mammography sensitivity is reduced.[190–192] Teaching opportunities in ultrasound include comparing acoustic impedance and contrast mechanisms across different tissue

types, discussing the advantages of real-time imaging for procedure guidance, and analyzing Doppler shift calculations

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is the gold standard for evaluating suspected soft tissue masses and structural abnormalities, including reproductive tract cancers and uterine septal anomalies. While not a front line imaging modality in pregnancy, MRI has been used to evaluate fetal abnormalities and placental disorders such as placenta accreta,[193] and has more recently been reported to provide structural assessment of ovarian reserve in cases of premature ovarian failure.[194] Dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA) is one of the most widely performed structural imaging procedures in women's health, used to assess bone mineral density for osteoporosis diagnosis and monitoring across the menopausal transition.[195] Fallopian tube patency, as well as uterus shape and lining, is also typically assessed via X-ray-based hysterosalpingography but radiation-free alternatives are currently being assessed to avoid potential risk of fetal harm.[196] These examples could enable discussions surrounding the clinical utility and safety of ionizing and non-ionizing imaging modalities.

Optical methods offer complementary capabilities where ionizing radiation is undesirable and when structural, functional, or chemical information is required at relatively shallow depths (hundreds of micrometers to centimeters). Diffuse optical tomography and near-infrared spectroscopy use multiply scattered light to probe tissue optical properties at depth, on the order of several mm to cm, and have been applied to breast cancer detection, breast density quantification, tumor hemodynamic characterization without ionizing radiation, and more recently placental oxygenation.[176] Photoacoustic imaging, which combines pulsed laser excitation with ultrasound detection, generates high-resolution maps of hemoglobin concentration and oxygenation, and has been investigated for imaging ovarian blood flow, sentinel lymph node mapping in breast cancer staging, and noninvasive placental monitoring.[197, 198] Optical coherence tomography and light sheet imaging are also under investigation for embryo selection in IVF, with the goal of improving prediction of successful implantation.[199, 200]

Endoscopic imaging approaches are central to both the diagnosis and surgical treatment of gynecologic conditions, and the engineering challenges they present, in miniaturization, illumination, image quality, and real-time processing, making them valuable course examples. Colposcopy is a wide-field technique that provides surface level visual inspection of the cervix, helping to reveal dysplastic tissue and guiding biopsy for the detection of cervical precancers and cancer.[201] Engineering advances in colposcope miniaturization and cost reduction are active areas of development, particularly for use in low-resource settings where the cervical cancer burden is highest.[119] Hysteroscopy enables direct visualization of the uterine cavity for identification and resection of fibroids, polyps, and adhesions, while cystoscopy supports

bladder evaluation for applications including cancer detection, interstitial cystitis, and pelvic pain. Laparoscopic and robotic surgery rely on high-definition pelvic video imaging and are the primary modalities for treating endometriosis, ovarian cysts, and ectopic pregnancy. Fluorescence-enhanced laparoscopy is under active investigation for intraoperative endometriosis lesion identification, where lesions are frequently indistinguishable from surrounding peritoneal tissue under white light alone.

J. Data Science

Clinical trials are expensive, and thus small in terms of number of participants. However, it has recently become clear that a vast quantity of data exists in medical records, which can be used to examine what are called “natural experiments,”[202] when observational studies are performed without explicit intervention. For example, data from medical records could be used to study populations who self-select into groups—for instance, individuals who take specific medications during pregnancy.[203] The use of existing medical records datasets is geographically distinguished based on whether any particular country has a homogeneous single-payer medical system (e.g. Sweden) versus a heterogeneous multi-payer system (e.g., the U.S.). There are also significant issues to do with privacy of medical records, which have in part led to the development of synthetic medical records[204] – de-identified medical records with the same statistical characteristics of the real records.

In engineering curricula, integrating women’s health topics into courses on data science provides a holistic perspective on utilizing medical records and big data to address sex-specific challenges. Students can gain hands-on experience by evaluating publicly available datasets focused on women’s health, learning to identify missing or under-represented populations. For example, courses can explore global disparities by analyzing incomplete data trends for reproductive health conditions in low- and middle-income countries. Similarly, students can develop sex-inclusive language and data input standards for health apps and wearable technologies, ensuring algorithms reflect sex-specific physiology and use equitable representation in training datasets. Big data also presents opportunities for revealing trends in challenging contexts, such as menstrual cycle data or fluctuating hormone profiles, which are often poorly tracked or inconsistently reported. Predictive algorithms for wearable technologies could be utilized to monitor these parameters in real-time, providing insights into menstrual cycles, fertility windows, or hormonal changes during pregnancy, menopause, or postpartum. Design projects could focus on leveraging data-driven approaches to create technologies that address unmet needs—for example, wearable devices that predict and alert individuals about patterns in conditions like polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) or endometriosis.

Ultimately, integrating women’s health-specific applications into data science engineering curriculum enables students to build predictive and analytical models that advance

personalized medicine while considering the ethical, technical, and global implications of working with sensitive data.

K. Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence

Machine learning in biomedical engineering can be applied to a wide range of data types, including lab test readouts,[205] radiographic images,[206] narrative medical practitioner notes,[207] and combinations of many data types (so called ‘multimodal’ data). The application of these techniques to problems in women’s health is a fast-growing area of investigation, both in research environments and in FemTech companies.

To aid with risk stratification and diagnosis of disorders affecting women, supervised learning has been a remarkably effective approach. This has been applied to predict the risk of preterm birth by incorporating other variables, such as cervical length measurements and patient history, with the goal of identifying high-risk pregnancies early enough to allow intervention.[208] Supervised models have also demonstrated strong performance on risk stratification for gestational diabetes[209] and preeclampsia,[210] sometimes outperforming traditional methods. Classification algorithms are also being allowed to the diagnosis of disorders where symptom heterogeneity makes pattern recognition challenging, such as endometriosis.[211, 212] These tools make it possible to identify (and possibly diagnose) chronic disorders in patients via symptom patterns well before the disease is recognized clinically. Image-based algorithms, such as those that use deep learning, have commercially advanced women’s health applications. For example, AI-assisted mammography tools have been shown to reduce both false positive and false negative rates.[213] Several deep learning models exist for colposcopy images and digitized Pap smears to screen for cervical cancer in low-resource settings.[214–216] Perhaps one of the best examples to date is AI-assisted embryo selection for in vitro fertilization. By training models on time-lapse morphometry images of developing embryos, researchers are able to better predict implantation potential, leading to higher numbers of successful pregnancies.[199, 200]

Digital twins represent an emerging frontier with relevance to long term monitoring and management. These are computational models that can simulate an individual’s physiology and can be updated with data to make real-time predictions and risk assessments. One potential avenue for digital twins has been proposed for pregnancy monitoring and management, enabling monitoring of cardiovascular changes and fetal growth trajectories.[217] It’s thought that this might revolutionize care and help predict preventable outcomes from treatable conditions such as preterm labor, gestational hypertension, and placental spectrum disorders. This could be expanded to many different disease conditions beyond pregnancy, such as chronic autoimmune or metabolic disorders. It’s important to point out here, though, that many models trained on datasets that underrepresent women of color, older women, or women in low-resource settings

can perpetuate and amplify existing disparities in diagnostic accuracy and clinical decision support. Biomedical engineers bear direct responsibility for evaluating the representativeness of training data, testing model performance across demographic subgroups, and advocating for regulatory standards that require disaggregated validation.

L. Synthetic Biology/Genetic Engineering

Synthetic biology and genetic engineering courses provide powerful opportunities to explore women's health applications at the molecular and cellular level. These courses typically cover topics including CRISPR gene editing, metabolic engineering, synthetic gene circuits, protein engineering, biosensor development, and microbiome manipulation, which have direct relevance to addressing women's health challenges. While synthetic approaches for women's health applications are still in early stages, they are useful educationally to illustrate both the therapeutic potential and ethical complexities of genetic manipulation, from germline editing considerations to equitable access to emerging therapies.

Gene editing modules can explore CRISPR-based interventions for hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndromes, discussing both somatic cell therapy for treatment and the ethical implications of germline editing for prevention.[218] Microbiome engineering provides rich opportunities to address vaginal microbiome health, with projects designing engineered *Lactobacillus* strains to prevent bacterial vaginosis or recurrent urinary tract infections—conditions that disproportionately affect women and remain challenging to treat with conventional antibiotics.[219] Biosensor modules can focus on developing cell-based or molecular sensors for pregnancy hormones (human chorionic gonadotropin, progesterone, placental growth factor), ovulation markers, or early detection of pregnancy complications like preeclampsia.[220] Throughout these applications, ethical discussions should address the complex considerations around reproductive genetics, access to emerging therapies, dual-use concerns, and the historical context of reproductive coercion, ensuring students develop both technical competency and ethical reasoning in this rapidly advancing field.

M. Ethics & Regulatory Considerations

Ethics and regulatory courses in biomedical engineering are designed to prepare students to navigate the frameworks governing the development, testing, approval, and post-market oversight of medical technologies. Women's health offers an exceptionally instructive body of case material—spanning device failures, clinical trial exclusion, contested regulatory pathways, and emerging reproductive technologies—where the intersection of engineering decisions, institutional policy, and patient outcomes is direct, well-documented, and consequential.

A foundational topic is the systematic exclusion of women from clinical drug trials following the thalidomide tragedy of the 1960s, in which a sedative prescribed to pregnant women caused severe fetal limb malformation.[221] Although precautionary in intent, this policy produced decades of drug approvals based on predominantly male data, contributing to uncharacterized sex differences in dosing, adverse effect profiles, and therapeutic efficacy. The FDA reversed this policy in the early 1990s but did not mandate sex-disaggregated reporting in clinical research until 2016. During this timeframe, many prescription drugs were withdrawn, or recommendations were changed because of health risks specific to women. The most well-known example is the change in recommended dose for the popular sleep aid, Ambien, after discovering metabolic differences between males and females that led to excessive daytime drowsiness.[222] This regulatory trajectory provides a compelling case study in how well-intentioned policy can produce inequitable outcomes, and how the absence of representative data at the research stage propagates downstream into clinical practice for decades.

Medical device case studies are equally instructive for demonstrating how regulatory pathways shape patient risk. The Dalkon Shield, discussed in the Biomaterials section, illustrates how inadequate preclinical material testing and insufficient regulatory scrutiny led to serious patient harm, and how its legacy shaped the reclassification of IUDs as Class III medical devices..[133] The transvaginal mesh controversy provides a more recent regulatory failure, where safety and efficacy in new anatomical contexts were not required for approval.[223] Subsequent reports of chronic pelvic pain, mesh erosion, organ perforation, and nerve injury led to mandatory market withdrawal in 2019. Students can use these cases to examine the trade-offs between premarket and post-market evidence requirements, the adequacy of informed consent when long-term risks are poorly characterized, and the professional responsibility of engineers when devices they help design reach market without sufficient validation.

Finally, there are a number of case studies in women's health that fuel conversations about bioethics. Assisted reproductive technologies introduce a rapidly evolving set of ethical challenges concerning equitable access, the commodification of reproductive materials, the legal and moral status of embryos, and the ethics of genetic selection for disease prevention or trait enhancement.[224] Gene editing technologies further complicate this, adding concerns about reproductive autonomy and informed consent for future persons. Contraceptive technologies also have rich histories entangled with racial disparities in both access and safety, cultural and religious considerations, and coercive research practices. As biomedical engineers expand into this space, ethics courses that use women's health case material will better prepare students for the broader professional responsibilities associated with health equity. Students trained to recognize where past frameworks have failed will be better equipped to advocate for stronger safeguards in future product development pipelines.

N. Design Courses

Design courses represent one of the most natural and impactful settings for integrating women's health into the engineering curriculum. Central to design education is the practice of customer discovery: the systematic engagement with end users, clinicians, and caregivers to identify and validate unmet needs before committing to a design direction. Structured interviews with patients experiencing conditions such as endometriosis, pelvic floor dysfunction, menopause symptoms, or infertility can reveal needs that are poorly represented in published literature and that may challenge students' assumptions about what constitutes a legitimate engineering problem.[225] Case studies of male-default design failures provide strong pedagogical motivation for inclusive, user-centered needs-finding. Commonly cited examples include crash test dummies historically based on male anthropometry, cardiovascular risk models and dosing guidelines derived from clinical trial populations that underrepresented or excluded women; and transvaginal surgical mesh products approved without female-specific clinical trial data.

Industry partnerships can substantially enrich the authenticity of capstone experiences. The FemTech sector, which encompasses companies developing technologies for menstrual health, fertility, pregnancy monitoring, pelvic health, sexual health, and menopause, is growing rapidly and may offer opportunities for faculty to engage companies as project clients who provide real design briefs, regulatory context, and end-user feedback. Local clinical partners—obstetricians, gynecologists, urogynecologists, midwives, or pelvic floor physical therapists—can serve as domain experts or user advocates throughout the design cycle. Where formal partnerships are not feasible, published clinical needs assessments can provide equivalent grounding for project scoping. Encouraging students to attend or participate in women's health-focused hackathons or design competitions is another avenue for authentic engagement with the problem space.

V. Conclusion

The landscape for educational content centered around the intersection of women's health and engineering is more favorable than ever. This review documents meaningful progress – a growing number of independently designed women's health engineering courses now exist, and women's health content is being woven into core biomedical engineering coursework in physiology, biomechanics, drug delivery, diagnostics, machine learning, and design. The practical pathways outlined in this review—both standalone courses and integrated content modules—are designed to lower the barrier for action, ensuring that institutions can begin implementing women's health engineering education regardless of their current capacity or constraints. The convergence of policy attention, research investment, industry growth, and student demand has created a rare window of

opportunity. The question for the biomedical engineering education community is not whether women's health belongs in the curriculum—this review makes clear that it does—but how quickly and comprehensively we choose to act. Engineers trained to recognize and address these gaps will not merely be better engineers; they will be the ones who build the technologies that generations of women have been waiting for.

VI. Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the review conception and design, data collection and analysis, and literature review. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

VII. Competing Interests

All authors certify that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

VIII. References

1. Submitter, E. R. V. A., and M. Oyen. Transforming Women's Health Outcomes through Engineering. , 2025. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5106554>
2. Closing the women's health gap | McKinseyat <<https://www.mckinsey.com/mhi/our-insights/closing-the-womens-health-gap-a-1-trillion-dollar-opportunity-to-improve-lives-and-economies>>
3. Kelly, A. J., J. Kavanagh, and J. Thomas. Castor oil, bath and/or enema for cervical priming and induction of labour. *Cochrane Database Syst. Rev.* 2013:CD003099, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD003099.pub2>
4. Karamanou, M., G. Tsoucalas, G. Creatsas, and G. Androustos. The effect of Soranus of Ephesus (98–138) on the work of midwives. *Women Birth* 26:226–228, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wombi.2013.08.160>
5. Nichols, F. H. History of the Women's Health Movement in the 20th Century. *J. Obstet. Gynecol. Neonatal Nurs.* 29:56–64, 2000. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.2000.tb02756.x>
6. Osuch, J. R., K. Silk, C. Price, J. Barlow, K. Miller, A. Hernick, and A. Fonfa. A historical perspective on breast cancer activism in the United States: from education and support to partnership in scientific research. *J. Womens Health* 2002 21:355–362, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1089/jwh.2011.2862>
7. Schubert, K. G., C. E. Bird, K. Kozhimmanil, and S. F. Wood. To Address Women's Health Inequity, It Must First Be Measured. *Health Equity* 6:881–886, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1089/heq.2022.0107>
8. Mirin, A. A. Gender Disparity in the Funding of Diseases by the U.S. National Institutes of Health. *J. Womens Health* 30:956–963, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1089/jwh.2020.8682>
9. Executive Order 14120—Advancing Women's Health Research and Innovation | The American Presidency Projectat <<https://www.presidency.ucsb.edu/documents/executive-order-14120-advancing-womens-health-research-and-innovation>>
10. A New Vision for Women's Health Researchat <<https://www.nationalacademies.org/projects/HMD-BPH-23-04>>

11. Beilmann, M., K. Adkins, H. C. M. Boonen, P. Hewitt, W. Hu, R. Mader, S. Moore, P. Rana, T. Steger-Hartmann, R. Villenave, and T. van Vleet. Application of new approach methodologies for nonclinical safety assessment of drug candidates. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* 24:705–725, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41573-025-01182-9>
12. Jacobs, N., and J. Evers. Ethical perspectives on femtech: Moving from concerns to capability-sensitive designs. *Bioethics* 37:430–439, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bioe.13148>
13. Grimm, M. J. Engineering and women’s health: a slow start, but gaining momentum. *Interface Focus* 9:20190017, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsfs.2019.0017>
14. Women’s Health Curricula: Final Report on Expert Panel Recommendations for Interprofessional Collaboration across the Health Professions. , 2015.at <<https://nexusipe.org/informing/resource-center/women%E2%80%99s-health-curricula-final-report-expert-panel-recommendations>>
15. Beddoes, K. Feminist methodologies and engineering education research. *Eur. J. Eng. Educ.* 38:107–118, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2012.748015>
16. Ellsworth, E. Why Doesn’t This Feel Empowering? Working Through the Repressive Myths of Critical Pedagogy. *Harv. Educ. Rev.* 59:297–325, 1989. <https://doi.org/10.17763/haer.59.3.058342114k266250>
17. Whose Science? Whose Knowledge? by Sandra G. Harding | Paperback at <<https://www.cornellpress.cornell.edu/book/9780801497469/whose-science-whose-knowledge/>>
18. Giddings, L. A., and C. Price. Feminist Pedagogy in STEM: The Intersection of STEM Pedagogy and Feminist Theory. *Fem. Pedagogy* 4:, 2023.at <https://scholarworks.smith.edu/chm_facpubs/94>
19. Whitehead, M. The Concepts and Principles of Equity and Health. *Int. J. Health Serv.* 22:429–445, 1992. <https://doi.org/10.2190/986L-LHQ6-2VTE-YRRN>
20. World Health Organization. A Conceptual Framework for Action on the Social Determinants of Health at <<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241500852>>
21. Prince, M. Does Active Learning Work? A Review of the Research. *J. Eng. Educ.* 93:223–231, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2004.tb00809.x>
22. Freeman, S., S. L. Eddy, M. McDonough, M. K. Smith, N. Okoroafor, H. Jordt, and M. P. Wenderoth. Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 111:8410–8415, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1319030111>
23. Rogers, N., and J. Henrich. Teaching women’s health into the 21st century. *Women Health* 37:11–21, 2003. https://doi.org/10.1300/J013v37n04_02
24. Barker, S. The use of healthcare disparities as a tool to teach BME undergraduates about the importance of social justice in biomedical design. , 2025.at <<https://peer.asee.org/the-use-of-healthcare-disparities-as-a-tool-to-teach-bme-undergraduates-about-the-importance-of-social-justice-in-biomedical-design>>
25. Statistics (NCSES), N. C. for S. and E. The State of U.S. Science and Engineering 2024. , 2024.at <<https://nces.nsf.gov/pubs/nsb20243/talent-u-s-and-global-stem-education-and-labor-force#s-e-higher-education-in-the-united-states>>
26. Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues at <<https://www.nuffieldbioethics.org/publication/genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-social-and-ethical-issues/>>
27. Huckvale, K., J. Torous, and M. E. Larsen. Assessment of the Data Sharing and Privacy Practices of Smartphone Apps for Depression and Smoking Cessation. *JAMA Netw. Open* 2:e192542, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2019.2542>

28. Obermeyer, Z., B. Powers, C. Vogeli, and S. Mullainathan. Dissecting racial bias in an algorithm used to manage the health of populations. *Science* 366:447–453, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aax2342>
29. GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators. Global burden of 87 risk factors in 204 countries and territories, 1990-2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Lancet Lond. Engl.* 396:1223–1249, 2020. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30752-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30752-2)
30. Sung, H., J. Ferlay, R. L. Siegel, M. Laversanne, I. Soerjomataram, A. Jemal, and F. Bray. Global Cancer Statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries. *CA. Cancer J. Clin.* 71:209–249, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21660>
31. Global strategy to accelerate the elimination of cervical cancer as a public health problemat <<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240014107>>
32. Arbyn, M., F. Verdoodt, P. J. F. Snijders, V. M. J. Verhoef, E. Suonio, L. Dillner, S. Minozzi, C. Bellisario, R. Banzi, F.-H. Zhao, P. Hillemanns, and A. Anttila. Accuracy of human papillomavirus testing on self-collected versus clinician-collected samples: a meta-analysis. *Lancet Oncol.* 15:172–183, 2014. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(13\)70570-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(13)70570-9)
33. WHO Consolidated Guideline on Self-Care Interventions for Health: Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2019.at <<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK544164/>>
34. Herreid, C. F., and N. A. Schiller. Case Studies and the Flipped Classroom. *J. Coll. Sci. Teach.* 42:62–66, 2013.
35. Roberts, C. W., R. Jin, C. Espelien, J. L. Forman, and P. Chernyavskiy. Seatbelt use trends by pregnancy status and state in the United States, 2011-2024. *Traffic Inj. Prev.* 26:S114–S120, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15389588.2025.2502824>
36. Mergler, O., C. Espelien, G. R. Booth, C. Roberts, P. Vakiel, S. Romani, H. Zhang, B. Pipkorn, G. P. Siegmund, P. A. Crompton, and J. Forman. Differences in shoulder belt fit for females versus males measured using upright open magnetic resonance imaging. *J. Biomech.* 185:112676, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2025.112676>
37. Abrams, M. Z., and C. R. Bass. Female vs. male relative fatality risk in fatal motor vehicle crashes in the US, 1975-2020. *PloS One* 19:e0297211, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0297211>
38. Potter, J. J., J. L. Sauer, C. L. Weisshaar, D. G. Thelen, and H.-L. Ploeg. Gender differences in bicycle saddle pressure distribution during seated cycling. *Med. Sci. Sports Exerc.* 40:1126–1134, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0b013e3181666eea>
39. Lin, Z.-J., H.-H. Wang, and C.-H. Chen. The Effect of Bicycle Saddle Widths on Saddle Pressure in Female Cyclists. *J. Sports Sci. Med.* 22:425–430, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.52082/jssm.2023.425>
40. Partin, S. N., K. A. Connell, S. Schrader, J. LaCombe, B. Lowe, A. Sweeney, S. Reutman, A. Wang, C. Toennis, A. Melman, M. Mikhail, and M. K. Guess. The bar sinister: does handlebar level damage the pelvic floor in female cyclists? *J. Sex. Med.* 9:1367–1373, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1743-6109.2012.02680.x>
41. Udo, E. O., N. P. A. Zuithoff, N. M. van Hemel, C. C. de Cock, T. Hendriks, P. A. Doevendans, and K. G. M. Moons. Incidence and predictors of short- and long-term complications in pacemaker therapy: the FOLLOWPACE study. *Heart Rhythm* 9:728–735, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2011.12.014>
42. Varadarajan, K. M., T. J. Gill, A. A. Freiberg, H. E. Rubash, and G. Li. Gender differences in trochlear groove orientation and rotational kinematics of human knees. *J. Orthop. Res. Off. Publ. Orthop. Res. Soc.* 27:871–878, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jor.20844>

43. Peipert, J. F., Q. Zhao, J. E. Allsworth, E. Petrosky, T. Madden, D. Eisenberg, and G. Secura. Continuation and satisfaction of reversible contraception. *Obstet. Gynecol.* 117:1105–1113, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AOG.0b013e31821188ad>
44. van Eijk, A. M., G. Zulaika, M. Lenchner, L. Mason, M. Sivakami, E. Nyothach, H. Unger, K. Laserson, and P. A. Phillips-Howard. Menstrual cup use, leakage, acceptability, safety, and availability: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet Public Health* 4:e376–e393, 2019. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(19\)30111-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(19)30111-2)
45. Phillips-Howard, P. A., E. Nyothach, F. O. Ter Kuile, J. Omoto, D. Wang, C. Zeh, C. Onyango, L. Mason, K. T. Alexander, F. O. Odhiambo, A. Eleveld, A. Mohammed, A. M. van Eijk, R. T. Edwards, J. Vulule, B. Faragher, and K. F. Laserson. Menstrual cups and sanitary pads to reduce school attrition, and sexually transmitted and reproductive tract infections: a cluster randomised controlled feasibility study in rural Western Kenya. *BMJ Open* 6:e013229, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-013229>
46. Auchincloss, L. C., S. L. Laursen, J. L. Branchaw, K. Eagan, M. Graham, D. I. Hanauer, G. Lawrie, C. M. McLinn, N. Pelaez, S. Rowland, M. Towns, N. M. Trautmann, P. Varma-Nelson, T. J. Weston, and E. L. Dolan. Assessment of Course-Based Undergraduate Research Experiences: A Meeting Report. *CBE—Life Sci. Educ.* 13:29–40, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.14-01-0004>
47. Prince, M. J., and R. M. Felder. Inductive Teaching and Learning Methods: Definitions, Comparisons, and Research Bases. *J. Eng. Educ.* 95:123–138, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2006.tb00884.x>
48. Voice of the Customer Videos: An Educational Tool to Identify Unmet Clinical Needs and Develop Empathy for Medical Device Users | Biomedical Engineering Education at <<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43683-025-00206-5>>
49. Thistlethwaite, J. E., D. Davies, S. Ekeocha, J. M. Kidd, C. MacDougall, P. Matthews, J. Purkis, and D. Clay. The effectiveness of case-based learning in health professional education. A BEME systematic review: BEME Guide No. 23. *Med. Teach.* 34:e421-444, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.3109/0142159X.2012.680939>
50. Teaching and the Case Method (Third Edition): Text, Cases, and Readings ^ 4030at <<https://store.hbr.org/product/teaching-and-the-case-method-third-edition-text-cases-and-readings/4030>>
51. Tannenbaum, C., R. P. Ellis, F. Eyssel, J. Zou, and L. Schiebinger. Sex and gender analysis improves science and engineering. *Nature* 575:137–146, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1657-6>
52. Clyne, A. M., and K. L. Billiar. Problem-Based Learning in Biomechanics: Advantages, Challenges, and Implementation Strategies. *J. Biomech. Eng.* 138:, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4033671>
53. Newstetter, W., and P. Benkeser. Learning Assessment In Problem Based Learning For Bme Students. , 2002.at <<https://peer.asee.org/learning-assessment-in-problem-based-learning-for-bme-students>>
54. Hmelo-Silver, C. E. Problem-Based Learning: What and How Do Students Learn? *Educ. Psychol. Rev.* 16:235–266, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:EDPR.0000034022.16470.f3>
55. Albanese, M. A., and S. Mitchell. Problem-based learning: a review of literature on its outcomes and implementation issues. *Acad. Med. J. Assoc. Am. Med. Coll.* 68:52–81, 1993. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00001888-199301000-00012>
56. Dochy, F., M. Segers, P. Van den Bossche, and D. Gijbels. Effects of problem-based learning: a meta-analysis. *Learn. Instr.* 13:533–568, 2003. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-4752\(02\)00025-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-4752(02)00025-7)
57. Kuzma, M. A., C. L. Rutenberg, E. Gracely, and L. Z. Nieman. The Effect of Incorporating Women’s Health into a PBL Curriculum on Students’ Tendencies to Identify Learning Issues in an Ambulatory Care Setting. *Acad. Med.* 72:913, 1997.

58. Kuppuswamy, R., and D. Mhakure. Project-based learning in an engineering-design course – developing mechanical- engineering graduates for the world of work. *Procedia CIRP* 91:565–570, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2020.02.215>
59. Blumenfeld, P. C., E. Soloway, R. W. Marx, J. S. Krajcik, M. Guzdial, and A. Palincsar. Motivating Project-Based Learning: Sustaining the Doing, Supporting the Learning. *Educ. Psychol.* 26:369–398, 1991. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.1991.9653139>
60. Golecki, H. M., J. R. Amos, and J. Bradley. Designing Capstone Experiences for Interdisciplinarity in Biomedical Engineering Education. , 2023.at <<https://peer.asee.org/designing-capstone-experiences-for-interdisciplinarity-in-biomedical-engineering-education>>
61. Barron, B. J. S., D. L. Schwartz, N. J. Vye, A. Moore, A. Petrosino, L. Zech, and J. D. Bransford. Doing With Understanding: Lessons From Research on Problem- and Project-Based Learning. *J. Learn. Sci.* 7:271–311, 1998. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508406.1998.9672056>
62. Brown, T. Design Thinking. , 2008.at <<https://readings.design/PDF/Tim%20Brown,%20Design%20Thinking.pdf>>
63. Wei, L., W. Zhang, and C. Lin. The study of the effectiveness of design-based engineering learning: the mediating role of cognitive engagement and the moderating role of modes of engagement. *Front. Psychol.* 14:, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1151610>
64. Zhang, W., Y. Guan, and Z. Hu. The efficacy of project-based learning in enhancing computational thinking among students: A meta-analysis of 31 experiments and quasi-experiments. *Educ. Inf. Technol.* 29:14513–14545, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12392-2>
65. Rosario, R., T. S. Hopper, and A. Huang-Saad. Applying Research-Based Teaching Strategies in a Biomedical Engineering Programming Course: Introduction to Computer Aided Diagnosis. *Biomed. Eng. Educ.* 2:41–59, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43683-021-00057-w>
66. Santos-Díaz, A., L. Montesinos, M. Barrera-Esparza, M. del Mar Perez-Desentis, and D. E. Salinas-Navarro. Implementing a challenge-based learning experience in a bioinstrumentation blended course. *BMC Med. Educ.* 24:510, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-024-05462-7>
67. Hung, W. Theory to reality: a few issues in implementing problem-based learning. *Educ. Technol. Res. Dev.* 59:529–552, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-011-9198-1>
68. Hadgraft, R. G., and A. Kolmos. Emerging learning environments in engineering education. *Australas. J. Eng. Educ.* 25:3–16, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1080/22054952.2020.1713522>
69. Dym, C. L., A. M. Agogino, O. Eris, D. D. Frey, and L. J. Leifer. Engineering Design Thinking, Teaching, and Learning. *J. Eng. Educ.* 94:103–120, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2005.tb00832.x>
70. Sánchez-García, R., and S. Reyes-de-Cózar. Enhancing Project-Based Learning: A Framework for Optimizing Structural Design and Implementation—A Systematic Review with a Sustainable Focus. *Sustainability* 17:4978, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17114978>
71. Liu, Z. Study on design and practice of PBL teaching model based on STEM education concept. *Sci. Rep.* 15:32876, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-18485-x>
72. Shehab, S., D. Bohn, L. O’Bryan, L. Lawrence, and M. Tissenbaum. Integrating Human-Centered Design into Undergraduate STEM Capstone Courses: A Food Product Development Case Study. *Educ. Sci.* 15:542, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15050542>
73. Afroogh, S., A. Esmalian, J. P. Donaldson, and A. Mostafavi. Empathic Design in Engineering Education and Practice: An Approach for Achieving Inclusive and Effective Community Resilience. *Sustainability* 13:4060, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13074060>

74. Hosking, I., K. Cornish, M. Bradley, and P. J. Clarkson. Empathic engineering: helping deliver dignity through design. *J. Med. Eng. Technol.* 39:388–394, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.3109/03091902.2015.1088090>
75. Lunn, S. J., C. L. Bell-Huff, and J. M. Le Doux. Learning to Care: Faculty Perspectives on Developing Empathy and Inclusive Mindsets in Biomedical Engineering. *Biomed. Eng. Educ.* 2:123–140, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43683-022-00077-0>
76. Lattuca, L. R., L. J. Voigt, and K. Q. Fath. Does Interdisciplinarity Promote Learning? Theoretical Support and Researchable Questions. *Rev. High. Educ.* 28:23–48, 2004.
77. W. H. Newell, “Decision-Making in Interdisciplinary studies,” In G. Morcol, Ed., *Handbook of Decision-Making*, Marcel Dekke, New York, 2007, pp. 245-265. - References - Scientific Research Publishingat
<<https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=787853>>
78. Beers, S. Z. 21st Century Skills: Preparing Students for THEIR Future. , 2011.at
<https://www.yinghuaacademy.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/21st_century_skills.pdf>
79. Froyd, J. E., and M. W. Ohland. Integrated Engineering Curricula. *J. Eng. Educ.* 94:147–164, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2005.tb00835.x>
80. Borrego, M., and L. K. Newswander. Characteristics of Successful Cross-disciplinary Engineering Education Collaborations. *J. Eng. Educ.* 97:123–134, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2008.tb00962.x>
81. Singh, A., D. Ferry, and S. Mills. Improving Biomedical Engineering Education Through Continuity in Adaptive, Experiential, and Interdisciplinary Learning Environments. *J. Biomech. Eng.* 140:, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4040359>
82. Howe, S., and J. Wilbarger. 2005 National Survey Of Engineering Capstone Design Courses. , 2006.at <<https://peer.asee.org/2005-national-survey-of-engineering-capstone-design-courses>>
83. Lave, J., and E. Wenger. *Situated Learning: Legitimate Peripheral Participation.* , 1991. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511815355>
84. Chaulagain, S., J. A. Liu, J. E. McCombs, and S. L. Klein. Sex differences in immune responses to viruses, bacteria and vaccines. *Nat. Immunol.* 27:660–673, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41590-026-02470-1>
85. Ouzounian, J. G., and U. Elkayam. Physiologic changes during normal pregnancy and delivery. *Cardiol. Clin.* 30:317–329, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccl.2012.05.004>
86. Paller, C. J., C. M. Campbell, R. R. Edwards, and A. S. Dobs. Sex-Based Differences in Pain Perception and Treatment. *Pain Med.* 10:289–299, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1526-4637.2008.00558.x>
87. Howe, D., S. G. Cone, J. A. Piedrahita, B. Collins, L. A. Fordham, E. H. Griffith, J. T. Spang, and M. B. Fisher. Sex-specific biomechanics and morphology of the anterior cruciate ligament during skeletal growth in a porcine model. *J. Orthop. Res.* 40:1853–1864, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jor.25207>
88. Sebastian, F., H. DelCiello, A. D. Pant, M. J. A. Girard, V. Pathak-Ray, S. K. Dorairaj, and R. Amini. Image-Based Inverse Modeling Analysis of Iris Stiffness Across Sex in Patients With a History of Primary Angle-Closure Disease. *ASME Open J. Eng.* 4:, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4068677>
89. Moseley, T., A. J. Hicks, E. M. Cosgriff-Hernandez, M. K. Rausch, and J. Hakim. Finite element modeling in obstetrics and gynecology: advances, applications, and challenges. *Front. Med.* 12:, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2025.1606989>
90. Martins, J. a. C., M. P. M. Pato, E. B. Pires, R. M. N. Jorge, M. Parente, and T. Mascarenhas. Finite element studies of the deformation of the pelvic floor. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 1101:316–334, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1389.019>
91. Olapojoye, A. O., S. Zaheri, A. Nostratinia, and F. Hassanipour. Predicting Milk Flow Behavior in Human Lactating Breast: An Integrated Machine Learning and Computational

- Fluid Dynamics Approach. *J. Biomech. Eng.* 147:051005, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4068077>
92. Yazdekhosti, S., E. C. LaVoy, and S. L. Gorniak. Assessing breast acceleration while using sports bras and conventional bras: A comparative analysis of measurement techniques. *J. Biomech.* 183:112640, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2025.112640>
 93. Xie, P.-P., B. István, and M. Liang. Sex-specific differences in biomechanics among runners: A systematic review with meta-analysis. *Front. Physiol.* 13:994076, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2022.994076>
 94. Richardson, L. S., A. K Kammala, M. M. Costantine, S. J. Fortunato, E. Radnaa, S. Kim, R. N. Taylor, A. Han, and R. Menon. Testing of drugs using human fetomaternal interface organ-on-chips provide insights into pharmacokinetics and efficacy. *Lab. Chip* 22:4574–4592, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2lc00691j>
 95. Plitman Mayo, R., J. Olsthoorn, D. S. Charnock-Jones, G. J. Burton, and M. L. Oyen. Computational modeling of the structure-function relationship in human placental terminal villi. *J. Biomech.* 49:3780–3787, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2016.10.001>
 96. Szuba, A., and S. G. Rockson. Lymphedema: anatomy, physiology and pathogenesis. *Vasc. Med.* 2:321–326, 1997. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1358863X9700200408>
 97. Davis, M. J., S. D. Zawieja, and P. D. King. Transport and Immune Functions of the Lymphatic System. *Annu. Rev. Physiol.* 87:151–172, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-physiol-022724-104908>
 98. Hamon, A., J. Guinard-Flament, A. Costa, A. Fischer, P. Faverdin, M. Gelé, A. Boudon, and S. Lemosquet. Dynamics of the lactose content and other osmotic agents in milk throughout lactation according to the cow's parity. *JDS Commun.* 6:432–437, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jdsc.2024-0717>
 99. Truchet, S., and E. Honvo-Houéto. Physiology of milk secretion. *Best Pract. Res. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.* 31:367–384, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beem.2017.10.008>
 100. Xiao, S., J. R. Coppeta, H. B. Rogers, B. C. Isenberg, J. Zhu, S. A. Olalekan, K. E. McKinnon, D. Dokic, A. S. Rashedi, D. J. Haisenleder, S. S. Malpani, C. A. Arnold-Murray, K. Chen, M. Jiang, L. Bai, C. T. Nguyen, J. Zhang, M. M. Laronda, T. J. Hope, K. P. Maniar, M. E. Pavone, M. J. Avram, E. C. Sefton, S. Getsios, J. E. Burdette, J. J. Kim, J. T. Borenstein, and T. K. Woodruff. A microfluidic culture model of the human reproductive tract and 28-day menstrual cycle. *Nat. Commun.* 8:14584, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14584>
 101. Claire, I., D. Anderson, C. M. Klapperich, W. Kuohung, and J. Y. Wong. Biomaterials and Contraception: Promises and Pitfalls. *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* 48:2113–2131, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10439-019-02402-1>
 102. Raia, N. R., S. L. Bakaysa, C. E. Ghezzi, M. D. House, and D. L. Kaplan. Ex vivo pregnant-like tissue model to assess injectable hydrogel for preterm birth prevention. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. B Appl. Biomater.* 108:468–474, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.b.34403>
 103. House, M., C. C. Sanchez, W. L. Rice, S. Socrate, and D. L. Kaplan. Cervical tissue engineering using silk scaffolds and human cervical cells. *Tissue Eng. Part A* 16:2101–2112, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ten.tea.2009.0457>
 104. Nkansah, A., A. Budhwani, N. Grammer, N. Ang, A. Fairley, S. P. Salazar, A. Y. Chowdary, A. Anand, S. Seidlits, J. Allen, and E. Cosgriff-Hernandez. Characterization of Sex-Based Differences in Integrin-Mediated Endothelial Cell Adhesion to Bioactive Hydrogels. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* 11:6515–6520, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbiomaterials.5c01461>
 105. Ensign, L. M., B. C. Tang, Y.-Y. Wang, T. A. Tse, T. Hoen, R. Cone, and J. Hanes. Mucus-penetrating nanoparticles for vaginal drug delivery protect against herpes simplex virus. *Sci. Transl. Med.* 4:138ra79, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.3003453>
 106. Elzinga, F. A., B. Khalili, D. J. Touw, J. R. Prins, P. Olinga, H. G. D. Leuvenink, H. van Goor, S. J. Gordijn, A. Nagelkerke, and P. Mian. Placenta-on-a-Chip as an In Vitro

- Approach to Evaluate the Physiological and Structural Characteristics of the Human Placental Barrier upon Drug Exposure: A Systematic Review. *J. Clin. Med.* 12:4315, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12134315>
107. Masello, M., Y. Ren, D. Erickson, and J. O. Giordano. An automated controlled-release device for intravaginal hormone delivery. *JDS Commun.* 1:15–20, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jdsc.2020-18816>
 108. Poley, M., G. Chen, N. Sharf-Pauker, A. Avital, M. Kaduri, M. Sela, P. M. Raimundo, L. Koren, S. Arber, E. Egorov, J. Shainsky, J. Shklover, and A. Schroeder. Sex-Based Differences in the Biodistribution of Nanoparticles and Their Effect on Hormonal, Immune, and Metabolic Function. *Adv. NanoBiomed Res.* 2:2200089, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anbr.202200089>
 109. Clifford, G. D., I. Silva, J. Behar, and G. B. Moody. Non-invasive fetal ECG analysis. *Physiol. Meas.* 35:1521–1536, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0967-3334/35/8/1521>
 110. Tekela, D. D., A. G. Asmare, B. M. Gebremariam, C. A. Assegahegn, K. D. Wami, H. D. Nemomssa, and G. L. Simegn. Digital postpartum hemorrhage management device (DPHMD). *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 19:438, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-019-2601-3>
 111. Tran, K. T., T. N. Tran, D. N. Huynh, N. K. Le, C. D. Le, H. X. Mai, Q. L. Huynh, and T. H. Nguyen. A Multimodal System for Comprehensive Cardiovascular Monitoring Using ECG, PCG, and PPG Signal Fusion. *Sensors* 25:6708, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25216708>
 112. Gombert-Labedens, M., E. Alzueta, E. Perez-Amparan, D. Yuksel, O. Kiss, M. de Zambotti, K. Simon, J. Zhang, A. Shuster, A. Morehouse, A. Alessandro Pena, S. Mednick, and F. C. Baker. Using Wearable Skin Temperature Data to Advance Tracking and Characterization of the Menstrual Cycle in a Real-World Setting. *J. Biol. Rhythms* 39:331–350, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07487304241247893>
 113. Posthuma-Trumpie, G. A., J. Korf, and A. van Amerongen. Lateral flow (immuno)assay: its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. A literature survey. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 393:569–582, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-008-2287-2>
 114. Gire, S., X. Li, C. Toth, M. Doshi, S. K. Gupta, S. Parker, D. Boles, and R. Tariyal. Unlocking uterine biology at home: a validated system for DNA, RNA, and microbial analysis from menstrual effluence. , 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.05.21.25327630>
 115. Ravel, J., P. Gajer, Z. Abdo, G. M. Schneider, S. S. K. Koenig, S. L. McCulle, S. Karlebach, R. Gorle, J. Russell, C. O. Tacket, R. M. Brotman, C. C. Davis, K. Ault, L. Peralta, and L. J. Forney. Vaginal microbiome of reproductive-age women. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 108 Suppl 1:4680–4687, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1002611107>
 116. Mann, R. M., C. K. Kuhl, and L. Moy. Contrast-enhanced MRI for breast cancer screening. *J. Magn. Reson. Imaging JMRI* 50:377–390, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmri.26654>
 117. Haghghat, H., M. Mirzarezaee, B. N. Araabi, and A. Khadem. A sex-dependent computer-aided diagnosis system for autism spectrum disorder using connectivity of resting-state fMRI. *J. Neural Eng.* 19:056034, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ac86a4>
 118. Gourlay, M. L., R. A. Overman, and K. E. Ensrud. Bone Density Screening and Re-screening in Postmenopausal Women and Older Men. *Curr. Osteoporos. Rep.* 13:390–398, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11914-015-0289-5>
 119. Lam, C. T., J. Mueller, B. Asma, M. Asiedu, M. S. Krieger, R. Chitalia, D. Dahl, P. Taylor, J. W. Schmitt, and N. Ramanujam. An integrated strategy for improving contrast, durability, and portability of a Pocket Colposcope for cervical cancer screening and diagnosis. *PLoS One* 13:e0192530, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0192530>
 120. Salomon, L. J., Z. Alfrevic, C. M. Bilardo, G. E. Chalouhi, T. Ghi, K. O. Kagan, T. K. Lau, A. T. Papageorghiou, N. J. Raine-Fenning, J. Stimemann, S. Suresh, A. Tabor, I. E. Timor-Tritsch, A. Toi, and G. Yeo. ISUOG practice guidelines: performance of first-trimester fetal

- ultrasound scan. *Ultrasound Obstet. Gynecol. Off. J. Int. Soc. Ultrasound Obstet. Gynecol.* 41:102–113, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1002/uog.12342>
121. Peters, S. A. E., and M. Woodward. A roadmap for sex- and gender-disaggregated health research. *BMC Med.* 21:354, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-023-03060-w>
 122. Bull, J. R., S. P. Rowland, E. B. Scherwitzl, R. Scherwitzl, K. G. Danielsson, and J. Harper. Real-world menstrual cycle characteristics of more than 600,000 menstrual cycles. *Npj Digit. Med.* 2:83, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-019-0152-7>
 123. Mohan, S., and J. Jenkins. Flowing data: women’s views and experiences on privacy and data security when using menstrual cycle tracking apps. *Oxf. Open Digit. Health* 3:oqaf011, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oodh/oqaf011>
 124. Kerr, K. E., I. Sen, P. H. Gueldner, T. Tallarita, J. C. Wildenberg, N. L. Liang, D. A. Vorp, and T. K. Chung. Sex-specific machine learning classification models improve outcome prediction for abdominal aortic aneurysms. *Biol. Sex Differ.* 16:96, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13293-025-00765-w>
 125. Liao, Z., C. Yan, J. Wang, N. Zhang, H. Yang, C. Lin, H. Zhang, W. Wang, and W. Li. A clinical consensus-compliant deep learning approach to quantitatively evaluate human in vitro fertilization early embryonic development with optical microscope images. *Artif. Intell. Med.* 149:102773, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2024.102773>
 126. Dibaji, M., J. Ospel, R. Souza, and M. Bento. Sex differences in brain MRI using deep learning toward fairer healthcare outcomes. *Front. Comput. Neurosci.* 18:, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2024.1452457>
 127. Scott, A. K., and M. L. Oyen. Virtual pregnancies: predicting and preventing pregnancy complications with digital twins. *Lancet Digit. Health* 6:e436–e437, 2024. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(24\)00086-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(24)00086-4)
 128. Kumar, N. Genome Editing in Gynecological Oncology: The Emerging Role of CRISPR/Cas9 in Precision Cancer Therapy. *Ther. Innov. Regul. Sci.* 59:937–948, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43441-025-00807-w>
 129. Lagenaur, L. A., B. E. Sanders-Bear, B. Brichacek, R. Pal, X. Liu, Y. Liu, R. Yu, D. Venzon, P. P. Lee, and D. H. Hamer. Prevention of vaginal SHIV transmission in macaques by a live recombinant *Lactobacillus*. *Mucosal Immunol.* 4:648–657, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1038/mi.2011.30>
 130. McNerney, M. P., K. E. Doiron, T. L. Ng, T. Z. Chang, and P. A. Silver. Theranostic cells: emerging clinical applications of synthetic biology. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 22:730–746, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41576-021-00383-3>
 131. Zhao, H., M. DiMarco, K. Ichikawa, M. Boulicault, M. Perret, K. Jillson, A. Fair, K. DeJesus, and S. S. Richardson. Making a “sex-difference fact”: Ambien dosing at the interface of policy, regulation, women’s health, and biology. *Soc. Stud. Sci.* 53:475–494, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03063127231168371>
 132. Mao, J., B. Chughtai, S. Ibrahim, and A. Sedrakyan. Food and Drug Administration Safety Communication on the Use of Transvaginal Mesh in Pelvic Organ Prolapse Repair Surgery: The Impact of Social Determinants of Health. *Female Pelvic Med. Reconstr. Surg.* 27:e133–e138, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1097/SPV.0000000000000863>
 133. Tatum, H. J., F. H. Schmidt, D. Phillips, M. McCarty, and W. M. O’Leary. The Dalkon Shield controversy. Structural and bacteriological studies of IUD tails. *JAMA* 231:711–717, 1975. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.231.7.711>
 134. Brezina, P. R., and Y. Zhao. The ethical, legal, and social issues impacted by modern assisted reproductive technologies. *Obstet. Gynecol. Int.* 2012:686253, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/686253>
 135. Rooney, S. I., and S. M. Jelenewicz. Voice of the Customer Videos: An Educational Tool to Identify Unmet Clinical Needs and Develop Empathy for Medical Device Users. *Biomed. Eng. Educ.* 6:153–169, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43683-025-00206-5>

136. Facca, D., J. Hall, G. Teachman, J. Redden, and L. Donelle. Femtech in context: A critical conceptual (re)view. *Health (N. Y.)* 30:369–388, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13634593251371327>
137. Perez, C. C. *Invisible Women: Data Bias in a World Designed for Men*. London: Abrams Press, 2020, 272 pp.
138. Phillips, S. P., K. Gee, and L. Wells. Medical Devices, Invisible Women, Harmful Consequences. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 19:14524, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192114524>
139. Schauburger, C. W., B. L. Rooney, L. Goldsmith, D. Shenton, P. D. Silva, and A. Schaper. Peripheral joint laxity increases in pregnancy but does not correlate with serum relaxin levels. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.* 174:667–671, 1996. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9378\(96\)70447-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9378(96)70447-7)
140. Liu, X. S., L. Wang, C. M. J. de Bakker, and X. Lai. Mechanical Regulation of the Maternal Skeleton during Reproduction and Lactation. *Curr. Osteoporos. Rep.* 17:375–386, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11914-019-00555-5>
141. Kaissar, M. S., and K. Yoshida. Computational model captures cardiac growth in hypertensive pregnancies and in the postpartum period. *Am. J. Physiol. Heart Circ. Physiol.* 326:H1491–H1497, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00104.2024>
142. Duarte, C. A., S. Fang, I. M. Rosado-Mendez, G. Ateshian, T. J. Hall, H. Feltovich, and K. M. Myers. An Anisotropic Reactive Viscoelastic Model of the Rhesus Macaque Cervix for Studying Cervical Remodeling. *J. Biomech. Eng.* 148:011006, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4070349>
143. Claire, I., D. Anderson, C. M. Klapperich, W. Kuohung, and J. Y. Wong. Biomaterials and Contraception: Promises and Pitfalls. *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* 48:2113–2131, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10439-019-02402-1>
144. Fogg, K., N.-H. Tseng, S. R. Peyton, P. Holeman, S. Mc Loughlin, J. P. Fisher, A. Sutton, A. Shikanov, J. S. Gnecco, K. M. Knight, E. M. Slaby, J. D. Weaver, N. N. Hashemi, Y. Zhang, M. D. House, B. J. Vogt, B. A. Aguado, J. C. Bradford, J. L. Robinson, P. K. Thomas, A. G. Lau, and M. L. Oyen. Roadmap on biomaterials for women’s health. *J. Phys. Mater.* 6:012501, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7639/ac90ee>
145. Francés-Herrero, E., E. Juárez-Barber, H. Campo, S. López-Martínez, L. de Miguel-Gómez, A. Faus, A. Pellicer, H. Ferrero, and I. Cervelló. Improved Models of Human Endometrial Organoids Based on Hydrogels from Decellularized Endometrium. *J. Pers. Med.* 11:504, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm11060504>
146. Zambuto, S. G., K. B. H. Clancy, and B. A. C. Harley. A gelatin hydrogel to study endometrial angiogenesis and trophoblast invasion. *Interface Focus* 9:20190016, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsfs.2019.0016>
147. Gnecco, J. S., A. Brown, K. Buttrey, C. Ives, B. A. Goods, L. Baugh, V. Hernandez-Gordillo, M. Loring, K. B. Isaacson, and L. G. Griffith. Organoid co-culture model of the human endometrium in a fully synthetic extracellular matrix enables the study of epithelial-stromal crosstalk. *Med* 4:554-579.e9, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medj.2023.07.004>
148. Hoffman, T., A. Khademhosseini, and R. Langer. Chasing the Paradigm: Clinical Translation of 25 Years of Tissue Engineering. *Tissue Eng. Part A* 25:679–687, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ten.TEA.2019.0032>
149. Çevrim, Ç., N. J. Hilgert, A. M. Kaage, A. J. C. Russell, A. E. Goldstein, C. J. Ang, J. L. R. Gable, L. E. Bagamery, A. Breznik, D. J. D. Bella, M. Talay, J. Peng, K. E. O’Neill, F. Chen, S. R. Eddy, and K. L. McKinley. Induction of menstruation in mice reveals the regulation of menstrual shedding. , 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.10.08.681007>
150. Gilmer, G., Z. R. Hettinger, Y. Tuakli-Wosornu, E. Skidmore, J. K. Silver, R. C. Thurston, D. A. Lowe, and F. Ambrosio. Female aging: when translational models don’t translate. *Nat. Aging* 3:1500–1508, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43587-023-00509-8>

151. Marr, E. E., J. S. Gnecco, S. A. Missmer, S. M. Hawkins, K. G. Osteen, L. Hummelshoj, E. Greaves, K. L. Bruner-Tran, and for the EPHect Experimental Models Working Group. WERF Endometriosis Phenome and Biobanking Harmonisation Project for Experimental Models in Endometriosis Research (EPHect-EM-Organoids): endometrial organoids as an emerging technology for endometriosis research. *Mol. Hum. Reprod.* 31:gaaf024, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molehr/gaaf024>
152. Gnecco, J. S., A. T. Brown, E. L. Kan, L. Baugh, C. Ives, M. Loring, and L. G. Griffith. Physiomimetic Models of Adenomyosis. *Semin. Reprod. Med.* 38:179–196, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0040-1719084>
153. Edington, C. D. *et al.* Interconnected Microphysiological Systems for Quantitative Biology and Pharmacology Studies. *Sci. Rep.* 8:4530, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-22749-0>
154. Woodruff, T. K. What we could not have known: ovarian cycles, follicle development, and the signature of life. *Mol. Hum. Reprod.* 32:gaag010, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molehr/gaag010>
155. Chavoshinezhad, N., and B. Niknafs. Innovations in 3D ovarian and follicle engineering for fertility preservation and restoration. *Mol. Biol. Rep.* 51:1004, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11033-024-09783-0>
156. Mauvais-Jarvis, F., H. K. Berthold, I. Campesi, J.-J. Carrero, S. Dakal, F. Franconi, I. Gouni-Berthold, M. L. Heiman, A. Kautzky-Willer, S. L. Klein, A. Murphy, V. Regitz-Zagrosek, K. Reue, and J. B. Rubin. Sex- and Gender-Based Pharmacological Response to Drugs. *Pharmacol. Rev.* 73:730–762, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1124/pharmrev.120.000206>
157. Bosch, E. L., I. E. C. Sommer, and D. J. Touw. The influence of female sex and estrogens on drug pharmacokinetics: what is the evidence? *Expert Opin. Drug Metab. Toxicol.* 21:637–647, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17425255.2025.2481891>
158. Chu, T. Gender Differences in Pharmacokinetics. *US Pharm* 39:40–43, 2014.
159. McCoy, M. Multitissue analysis of absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion gene expression: Sex and age effects across human organ systems. *Drug Metab. Dispos.* 53:, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dmd.2025.100162>
160. Sameni, R., C. Jutten, and M. B. Shamsollahi. Multichannel Electrocardiogram Decomposition Using Periodic Component Analysis. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 55:1935–1940, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2008.919714>
161. Moghimikandelousi, S., L. Najm, Y. Lee, F. Bayat, A. Prasad, S. Khan, A. Bhavan, W. Gao, Z. Hosseinidoust, and T. F. Didar. Advances in biomonitoring technologies for women’s health. *Nat. Commun.* 16:8507, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-63501-3>
162. Sameni, R., and G. D. Clifford. A Review of Fetal ECG Signal Processing; Issues and Promising Directions. *Open Pacing Electrophysiol. Ther. J.* 3:4–20, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1876536X01003010004>
163. Rabotti, C., M. Mischi, S. G. Oei, and J. W. M. Bergmans. Noninvasive estimation of the electrohysterographic action-potential conduction velocity. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 57:2178–2187, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2010.2049111>
164. Rabotti, C., and M. Mischi. Propagation of electrical activity in uterine muscle during pregnancy: a review. *Acta Physiol.* 213:406–416, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apha.12424>
165. Kim, J., A. S. Campbell, B. E.-F. de Ávila, and J. Wang. Wearable biosensors for healthcare monitoring. *Nat. Biotechnol.* 37:389–406, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-019-0045-y>
166. Khelifa, L., Y. Hu, N. Jiang, and A. K. Yetisen. Lateral flow assays for hormone detection. *Lab. Chip* 22:2451–2475, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1lc00960e>
167. Stefańska, K., M. Zieliński, D. Zamkowska, P. Adamski, J. Jassem-Bobowicz, K. Piekarska, M. Jankowiak, K. Leszczyńska, R. Świątkowska-Stodulska, K. Preis, P.

- Trzonkowski, and N. Marek-Trzonkowska. Comparisons of Dipstick Test, Urine Protein-to-Creatine Ratio, and Total Protein Measurement for the Diagnosis of Preeclampsia. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 17:, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17124195>
168. Fritzenwanker, M., C. Imirzalioglu, T. Chakraborty, and F. M. Wagenlehner. Modern diagnostic methods for urinary tract infections. *Expert Rev. Anti Infect. Ther.* 14:1047–1063, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14787210.2016.1236685>
 169. Petrucelli, N., M. B. Daly, and T. Pal. BRCA1- and BRCA2-Associated Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer. In: GeneReviews®, edited by M. P. Adam, S. Bick, G. M. Mirzaa, R. A. Pagon, S. E. Wallace, and A. Amemiya. Seattle (WA): University of Washington, Seattle, 1993. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1247/>
 170. Charkhchi, P., C. Cybulski, J. Gronwald, F. O. Wong, S. A. Narod, and M. R. Akbari. CA125 and Ovarian Cancer: A Comprehensive Review. *Cancers* 12:, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers12123730>
 171. Takahashi, K., T. Shibukawa, M. Moriyama, T. Shirai, S. Kijima, O. Iwanari, I. Matsunaga, and M. Kitao. Clinical usefulness and false-positive results of CA 125 as a tumor marker of ovarian cancer—a study on 674 patients. *Jpn. J. Surg.* 16:305–310, 1986. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02470551>
 172. Paterson, E. S. J., S. Scheck, T. Kleffmann, R. Gill, N. Bedford, S. McDowell, J. E. Girling, and C. E. Henry. Proteomic Analysis of Cervicovaginal Fluid for Diagnostic Endometriosis Biomarker Discovery. *Proteomics Clin. Appl.* 20:e70044, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prca.70044>
 173. Parry, S., R. Leite, M. S. Esplin, R. Bukowski, H. Zhang, M. Varner, W. W. Andrews, G. R. Saade, J. Ileki, U. M. Reddy, H. Huang, Y. Sadovsky, I. A. Blair, J. Biggio, and Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development Genomic and Proteomic Network for Preterm Birth Research. Cervicovaginal fluid proteomic analysis to identify potential biomarkers for preterm birth. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.* 222:493.e1-493.e13, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2019.11.1252>
 174. Jiang, H., J. Qu, N. Huang, Z. Li, X. Shi, L. Chen, and Y. Zhao. Integrative multi-omic analysis reveals potential biomarkers in the cervicovaginal fluid of patients with placenta accrete spectrum. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 24:856, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-024-07065-y>
 175. Garrett, A., A. Perez, R. Ayalon, J. Forman, N. Hamburg, D. Boas, and D. Roblyer. Optical methods for cuffless blood pressure measurements. *Biophotonics Discov.* 3:010901, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.BIOS.3.1.010901>
 176. Schwartz, N., L. Wang, J. Cochran, T. Ko, W. Baker, K. Abramson, S. Parry, and A. Yodh. Novel optical tool for assessment of human placental oxygenation detects placental dysfunction in second trimester. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.* 226:S60–S61, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2021.11.125>
 177. Macnab, A., L. Stothers, and E. Deegan. Development of a near-infrared spectroscopy interface able to assess oxygen recovery kinetics in the right and left sides of the pelvic floor. *J. Biomed. Opt.* 24:075003, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JBO.24.7.075003>
 178. Fantini, S., and A. Sassaroli. Near-Infrared Optical Mammography for Breast Cancer Detection with Intrinsic Contrast. *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* 40:398–407, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10439-011-0404-4>
 179. Bonetta-Misteli, F., T. Collins, T. Pavek, M. Carlgren, D. Bashe, A. Frolova, L. Shmuylovich, and C. M. O'Brien. Development and evaluation of a wearable peripheral vascular compensation sensor in a swine model of hemorrhage. *Biomed. Opt. Express* 14:5338–5357, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1364/BOE.494720>
 180. Premasiri, W. R., Y. Chen, P. M. Williamson, D. C. Bandarage, C. Pyles, and L. D. Ziegler. Rapid urinary tract infection diagnostics by surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy

- (SERS): identification and antibiotic susceptibilities. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 409:3043–3054, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-017-0244-7>
181. Rourke-Funderburg, A. S., A. Mahadevan-Jansen, and A. K. Locke. Characterization of vaginal Lactobacillus in biologically relevant fluid using surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy. *Analyst* 149:4862–4871, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4AN00854E>
 182. Thigpen, N., S. Patel, and X. Zhang. Oura Ring as a Tool for Ovulation Detection: Validation Analysis. *J. Med. Internet Res.* 27:e60667, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.2196/60667>
 183. Zhao, L., C. Liang, Y. Huang, G. Zhou, Y. Xiao, N. Ji, Y.-T. Zhang, and N. Zhao. Emerging sensing and modeling technologies for wearable and cuffless blood pressure monitoring. *Npj Digit. Med.* 6:93, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-023-00835-6>
 184. Hadar, E., T. Biron-Shental, O. Gavish, O. Raban, and Y. Yogev. A comparison between electrical uterine monitor, tocodynamometer and intra uterine pressure catheter for uterine activity in labor. *J. Matern. Fetal Neonatal Med.* 28:1367–1374, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.3109/14767058.2014.954539>
 185. El-Sayegh, B., C. Dumoulin, M. Ali, H. Assaf, J. De Jong, M. Sawan, and F. Leduc-Primeau. Portable Dynamometer-Based Measurement of Pelvic Floor Muscle Force. *IEEE J. Transl. Eng. Health Med.* 11:44–53, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JTEHM.2022.3223258>
 186. Derchi, L. E., G. Serafini, N. Gandolfo, N. G. Gandolfo, and C. Martinoli. Ultrasound in gynecology. *Eur. Radiol.* 11:2137–2155, 2001. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s003300101080>
 187. Zamah, A. M., R. Power, R. E. Longman, and J. S. Abramowicz. Ultrasound and Infertility. In: *First-Trimester Ultrasound: A Comprehensive Guide*, edited by J. S. Abramowicz, and R. E. Longman. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2023, pp. 31–50. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-24133-8_3
 188. Hessami, K., E. D'Alberti, D. D. Mascio, and V. Berghella. Universal cervical length screening and risk of spontaneous preterm birth: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol. MFM* 6:, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajogmf.2024.101343>
 189. Leung, K.-Y. Applications of Advanced Ultrasound Technology in Obstetrics. *Diagnostics* 11:, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics11071217>
 190. Guo, R., G. Lu, B. Qin, and B. Fei. Ultrasound Imaging Technologies for Breast Cancer Detection and Management: A Review. *Ultrasound Med. Biol.* 44:37–70, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultrasmedbio.2017.09.012>
 191. Bahl, M. Screening for Breast Cancer: Imaging Updates. *Radiol. Clin. North Am.* 64:443–452, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcl.2026.01.003>
 192. Tuite, C. M., and S. C. Gavenonis. Digital Breast Tomosynthesis: What We now Know Beyond the Prevalent Screen. *J. Breast Imaging* wbag007, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jbi/wbag007>
 193. Bartels, H. C., D. P. Brophy, P. Downey, D. O'Brien, S. M. Corcoran, J. Donnelly, J. M. Walsh, T. Geoghegan, and D. J. Brennan. Use of magnetic resonance imaging as an adjunct to ultrasound for prenatal detection of placenta accreta spectrum. *Eur. J. Obstet. Gynecol. Reprod. Biol.* 321:115077, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2026.115077>
 194. Önal, M., A. Kocaman, Y. Katırcı, İ. Çamlıdağ, H. Ekici, and A. Bakay. A novel magnetic resonance imaging index to evaluate ovarian reserve in endometrioma patients: the ovary to endometrioma volume index. *Front. Med.* 13:1760689, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2026.1760689>
 195. Gourlay, M. L., R. A. Overman, and K. E. Ensrud. Bone Density Screening and Re-screening in Postmenopausal Women and Older Men. *Curr. Osteoporos. Rep.* 13:390–398, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11914-015-0289-5>
 196. Fu, Q., Z. Zhou, D. Ouyang, G. Chen, Y. Huang, Y. Lin, and Y. Yuan. Multimodal hysterosalpingo-contrast sonography in the assessment of fallopian tubal patency: A retrospective study. *Afr. J. Reprod. Health* 30:115–124, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.29063/ajrh2026/v30i6.11>

197. Lin, Y., L. Wang, I. S. Hagemann, L. M. Kuroki, B. E. Sanders, A. R. Hagemann, C. Siegel, M. A. Powell, and Q. Zhu. Vascular graph network for ovarian lesion classification using optical-resolution photoacoustic microscopy. *Photoacoustics* 47:100794, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pacs.2025.100794>
198. Wang, L., Y. Lin, S. Thakur, J. Xu, and Q. Zhu. Characterization of vascular patterns in endometrial cancer via optical resolution photoacoustic microscopy. *J. Biomed. Opt.* 31:045002, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JBO.31.4.045002>
199. McLennan, H. J., A. Saini, K. R. Dunning, and J. G. Thompson. Oocyte and embryo evaluation by AI and multi-spectral auto-fluorescence imaging: Livestock embryology needs to catch-up to clinical practice. *Theriogenology* 150:255–262, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2020.01.061>
200. Liao, Z., C. Yan, J. Wang, N. Zhang, H. Yang, C. Lin, H. Zhang, W. Wang, and W. Li. A clinical consensus-compliant deep learning approach to quantitatively evaluate human in vitro fertilization early embryonic development with optical microscope images. *Artif. Intell. Med.* 149:102773, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2024.102773>
201. DiSilvestro, J. B., A. Scott, A. P. Novetsky, and R. B. Perkins. A Lens into the Quality Standards of Modern-Day Colposcopy. *Obstet. Gynecol. Clin. North Am.* 53:121–138, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ogc.2025.09.009>
202. de Vocht, F., S. V. Katikireddi, C. McQuire, K. Tilling, M. Hickman, and P. Craig. Conceptualising natural and quasi experiments in public health. *BMC Med. Res. Methodol.* 21:32, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-021-01224-x>
203. Fortinguerra, F., V. Belleudi, F. R. Poggi, S. Perna, R. Bortolus, S. Donati, P. D'Aloja, R. D. Cas, A. Clavenna, A. Locatelli, A. Addis, M. Davoli, F. Trotta, and M.-N. Group. Monitoring medicine prescriptions before, during and after pregnancy in Italy. *PLOS ONE* 18:e0287111, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0287111>
204. Gonzales, A., G. Guruswamy, and S. R. Smith. Synthetic data in health care: A narrative review. *PLOS Digit. Health* 2:e0000082, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000082>
205. Bar, A., R. Moran, N. Mendelsohn-Cohen, Y. Korem Kohanim, A. Mayo, Y. Toledano, and U. Alon. Pregnancy and postpartum dynamics revealed by millions of lab tests. *Sci. Adv.* 11:eadr7922, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adr7922>
206. Zhou, S. K., H. Greenspan, C. Davatzikos, J. S. Duncan, B. van Ginneken, A. Madabhushi, J. L. Prince, D. Rueckert, and R. M. Summers. A review of deep learning in medical imaging: Imaging traits, technology trends, case studies with progress highlights, and future promises. *Proc. IEEE Inst. Electr. Electron. Eng.* 109:820–838, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2021.3054390>
207. Yang, X., A. Chen, N. PourNejatian, H. C. Shin, K. E. Smith, C. Parisien, C. Compas, C. Martin, A. B. Costa, M. G. Flores, Y. Zhang, T. Magoc, C. A. Harle, G. Lipori, D. A. Mitchell, W. R. Hogan, E. A. Shenkman, J. Bian, and Y. Wu. A large language model for electronic health records. *Npj Digit. Med.* 5:194, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-022-00742-2>
208. Koivu, A., and M. Sairanen. Predicting risk of stillbirth and preterm pregnancies with machine learning. *Health Inf. Sci. Syst.* 8:14, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13755-020-00105-9>
209. Yang, J., D. Clifton, J. E. Hirst, F. K. Kavvoura, G. Farah, L. Mackillop, and H. Lu. Machine Learning-Based Risk Stratification for Gestational Diabetes Management. *Sensors* 22:4805, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22134805>
210. Payne, B. A., J. A. Hutcheon, J. M. Ansermino, D. R. Hall, Z. A. Bhutta, S. Z. Bhutta, C. Biryabarema, W. A. Grobman, H. Groen, F. Haniff, J. Li, L. A. Magee, M. Merialdi, A. Nakimuli, Z. Qu, R. Sikandar, N. Sass, D. Sawchuck, D. W. Steyn, M. Widmer, J. Zhou, P. von Dadelszen, and miniPIERS Study Working Group. A risk prediction model for the

- assessment and triage of women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy in low-resourced settings: the miniPIERS (Pre-eclampsia Integrated Estimate of RiSk) multi-country prospective cohort study. *PLoS Med.* 11:e1001589, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001589>
211. Zhang, H., H. Zhang, H. Yang, A. N. Shuid, D. Sandai, and X. Chen. Machine learning-based integrated identification of predictive combined diagnostic biomarkers for endometriosis. *Front. Genet.* 14:1290036, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2023.1290036>
 212. Zhao, N., T. Hao, F. Zhang, Q. Ni, D. Zhu, Y. Wang, Y. Shi, and X. Mi. Application of machine learning techniques in the diagnosis of endometriosis. *BMC Womens Health* 24:491, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-024-03334-2>
 213. Lamb, L. R., C. D. Lehman, S. Do, K. Kim, S. Langarica, and M. Bahl. Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Based Computer-Assisted Detection and Diagnosis for Mammography: An Evidence-Based Review of Food and Drug Administration (FDA)-Cleared Tools for Screening Digital Breast Tomosynthesis (DBT). *AI Precis. Oncol.* 1:195–206, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1089/aipo.2024.0022>
 214. Mahajan, P., and P. Kaur. Improving cervical cancer classification in PAP smear images with enhanced segmentation and deep progressive learning-based techniques. *Diagn. Cytopathol.* 52:313–324, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dc.25295>
 215. Atteia, G., M. Alabdulhafith, H. A. Abdallah, N. Abdel Samee, and W. Alayed. Deep learning-based decision support system for cervical cancer identification in liquid-based cytology pap smears. *Technol. Health Care Off. J. Eur. Soc. Eng. Med.* 33:2194–2210, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09287329251330081>
 216. N Diniz, D., M. T Rezende, A. G C Bianchi, C. M Carneiro, E. J S Luz, G. J P Moreira, D. M Ushizima, F. N S de Medeiros, and M. J F Souza. A Deep Learning Ensemble Method to Assist Cytopathologists in Pap Test Image Classification. *J. Imaging* 7:111, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging7070111>
 217. Scott, A. K., and M. L. Oyen. Virtual pregnancies: predicting and preventing pregnancy complications with digital twins. *Lancet Digit. Health* 6:e436–e437, 2024. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(24\)00086-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(24)00086-4)
 218. Kumar, N. Genome Editing in Gynecological Oncology: The Emerging Role of CRISPR/Cas9 in Precision Cancer Therapy. *Ther. Innov. Regul. Sci.* 59:937–948, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43441-025-00807-w>
 219. Lagenaur, L. A., B. E. Sanders-Bear, B. Brichacek, R. Pal, X. Liu, Y. Liu, R. Yu, D. Venzon, P. P. Lee, and D. H. Hamer. Prevention of vaginal SHIV transmission in macaques by a live recombinant Lactobacillus. *Mucosal Immunol.* 4:648–657, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1038/mi.2011.30>
 220. Mc Nerney, M. P., K. E. Doiron, T. L. Ng, T. Z. Chang, and P. A. Silver. Theranostic cells: emerging clinical applications of synthetic biology. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 22:730–746, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41576-021-00383-3>
 221. Kim, J. H., and A. R. Scialli. Thalidomide: the tragedy of birth defects and the effective treatment of disease. *Toxicol. Sci. Off. J. Soc. Toxicol.* 122:1–6, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfr088>
 222. Zhao, H., M. DiMarco, K. Ichikawa, M. Boulicault, M. Perret, K. Jillson, A. Fair, K. DeJesus, and S. S. Richardson. Making a ‘sex-difference fact’: Ambien dosing at the interface of policy, regulation, women’s health, and biology. *Soc. Stud. Sci.* 53:475–494, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03063127231168371>
 223. Mao, J., B. Chughtai, S. Ibrahim, and A. Sedrakyan. Food and Drug Administration Safety Communication on the Use of Transvaginal Mesh in Pelvic Organ Prolapse Repair Surgery: The Impact of Social Determinants of Health. *Female Pelvic Med. Reconstr. Surg.* 27:e133–e138, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1097/SPV.0000000000000863>

224. Brezina, P. R., and Y. Zhao. The Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues Impacted by Modern Assisted Reproductive Technologies. *Obstet. Gynecol. Int.* 2012:686253, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/686253>
225. Rooney, S. I., and S. M. Jelenewicz. Voice of the Customer Videos: An Educational Tool to Identify Unmet Clinical Needs and Develop Empathy for Medical Device Users. *Biomed. Eng. Educ.* 6:153–169, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43683-025-00206-5>